

DISCUS PROJECT 21470018

DISCUS PROJECT FINAL REPORT (STUDY)

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Final Report
(Study)

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Abbreviations

ATU	- Administrative-Territorial Unit
BR	- Basic Registries
CMS	- Content Management System
CISC	- Citizen Information and Service Center
CPA	- Central Public Authority
DISCUS	- Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform
DS	- De-concentrated Services
EDIFACT	- Electronic Data Interchange For Administration Commerce and Transport
EGON	- System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic
ENI	- European Neighborhood Instrument
ENPI	- European Neighborhood Policy
ESC	- European Committee for Standardization
ETSI	- European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ERLS	- Electronic Registry of Local Services
GIS	- Geographical Information System
G2B	- Government to Business
G2C	- Government to Citizens
ICT	- Information & Communication Technologies
ICT4D	- ICT for Development
IDNO	- Juridical Person Identification Number
IDNP	- Physical Person Identification Number
IEC	- International Electro-technical Commission
INVIL	- Information Network Village Project
IS	- Information System
ISDI/IDSI	- Information Society Development Institute, Moldova
ISO	- International Organization for Standardization
ISPA	- Information System of the Public Administration
ITIL	- Information Technology Infrastructure Library
ITU	- International Telecommunications Union
JILDPA	- Joint Integrated Local Development Programme
LPA	- Local Public Authorities

PA	– Public Administration
PAR	– Public Administration Reform
PIAPs	– Public Internet Access Point
PMBOK	– Project Management Body of Knowledge
PPP	– Public-private Partnership
PRINCE2	– Projects In a Controlled Environment
PuP	Public-public partnership
RM	Republic of Moldova
SOA	– Service Oriented Architecture
TOGAF	– The Open Group Architecture Framework
UNDP	– United Nations Development Program
USAID	– U.S. Agency for International Development
V4	– Visegrad countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia

1. Introduction

During the last years information society issues became a central subject for discussions for Moldovan Government and other key-actors (business, civil society, research and education sector etc.). In spite of the existing <http://particip.gov.md/> platform, focused on involvement of civil society and government institutions in the decision-making process, feedback is scarce. Although half of population have computers and Internet access, only 12% use internet to access new regulatory documents and 11% access government websites.

The DISCUS Project platform is offering an excellent opportunity for all actors to discuss these issues with partners from Visegrad countries. The project "**DISCUSSION on Information Society Building Issues Platform**" aims at promoting the European model of effective application of information society policies/e-Governance tools in Moldova to strengthen participation of academic sector, local government, business, civil society, mass-media in decision making process, using the experience of V4 countries.

DISCUS project is financed under the International Visegrad Fund (contract no. 21470018) with a duration of one year – 2015. Project partners are:

[Information Society Development Institute, Republic of Moldova](#)

Information Society Development Institute (ISDI) is a research institute focused on research and applications for information society development. The Institute is the only R&D organization which is ISO 9001, ISO 14001, OHSAS 18001 and ISO 27001 certified. ISDI serves as information and consultancy source, cooperating extensively with individuals and businesses interested in building an information society at national, regional and international levels.

ISDI aims to become an institute of excellence, providing support through research and applications and acting as a cross-point for national and international organisations in areas of information and knowledge society.

[Information Society Development Foundation, Poland](#)

The Information Society Development Foundation is a non-governmental organization established in 2008 by the Polish-American Freedom Foundation. FRSI's objective is to support and promote the development of an information society with a very well developed services sector, high education standards, broad and inexpensive Internet access, public access to information, and the ability to exchange data irrespective of the distance. FRSI conducts activities to increase access of citizens, institutions and organizations to Internet-based information and communication technologies and strives to popularize the knowledge of the benefits of using those technologies in citizens' life.

FRSI carries out modernization projects aimed at involving the inhabitants of Polish villages and small towns in the main course of social and economic life and making it easier for them to gain access to information, knowledge and culture.

[proIS, s.r.o., Slovakia](#)

proIS was established in 2007 and has rich experience in areas such as the accession process of Slovakia to the EU (1999-2004), projects preparation and administration, building of information society and eGovernance. Some of the experts were involved in building the eGov infrastructure in Slovakia (National Conception of Informatic of Public Administration

and its national infrastructure, 2008) and in European bodies (European Environmental Agency, European Commission Task Forces and Working Groups, OECD Working Groups).

The company's today activities are still oriented on the work with information, providing them in user friendly format, combined for marketing purposes, using the power of internet, supporting SMEs and public institutions in project preparation support, fundraising, project administration and creating partnerships.

DATAB consult s.r.o., Czech Republic

DATAB consult was established in 1999 and company experts were working in Public Administration (State administration and Local self-government). The company has long term experience from implementation of information systems in Economy and Document management in Public administration.

DATAB consult is capable of providing support for solutions related to public finance management (methodology and implementation), document management, unification of data elements in information systems of public administration and their management, support of standardization.

The Final Report is based on DISCUS Project activities: seminars, workshops, study visits, discussions and research studies undertaken during 2015 in Chisinau, Moldova. The main sources for the Report:

- Approved DISCUS Project Document,
- TOR provisions,
- Own experience on best practices in Visegrad countries in ICT solutions for local services (with focus on planning and strategic aspects),
- Analyzed V4/EU countries experience/initiatives relevant to the DISCUS project objectives,
- Analysis of presented information and discussions during all project events,
- Analysis of issues, solutions, plans proposed by the local authorities representatives and other stakeholders expressed during all events from 2015,
- Analysis of ideas expressed during informal communication at all project events;
- Analysis of other relevant sources;
- 4 Project research studies: <http://discus.idsi.md/en/reports>
 1. **Recommendation on implementation of relevant Information System for Local Authorities (March - April 2015)**
 2. **Recommendations on Public Policies, Regulations/ Amendments for the relevant Public Authorities from the Republic of Moldova (June – July 2015)**
 3. **Recommendations on Local Public E-Services to be Developed (September – November 2015)**
 4. **Recommendations on action plan for implementation of local e-services (November – December 2015)**
- Analysis of the evaluation questionnaires completed by participants at all project events.

The Final Project Report is written within the DISCUS project as the result of all project activities during 2015.

The main goal of this Report is to present the consolidated project results and make them available for use by the local authorities in implementation of ICT based citizen-oriented services as well as to provide a vision on follow-up actions.

2. The impact of the project activities

To achieve the project objective aiming at promoting the European model of effective application of information society policies/e-Governance tools in Moldova to strengthen participation of academic sector, local government, business, civil society, mass-media in decision making process, using the experience of V4 countries a range of activities and events were undertaken.

A special communication platform (periodic seminar on Information Society development issues) was established to achieve the project goal and further facilitate political association with the EU.

The project was implemented through (*planned activities*):

- Delivery of 2 Workshops for local public representatives, civil society organisations and SMEs (involving study cases) on ICT-driven local development, aimed to identify relevant issues and enhance local participation in the decision-making process, with participation of V4 experts. Following each workshop a set of recommendations have been prepared on:
 - implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities
 - local e-services to be developed.
- Organisation of 2 Study visits in Visegrad countries of several visionaries selected from local public representatives, to support knowledge transfer and collaboration.
- Development of a draft action plan for implementation of local e-services in 2 selected rural localities, taking into account the opportunities for PPPs at the local level.
- Organisation of 2 Seminars with representatives of academic sector, government, business, civil society, mass-media and V4 experts on Information Society development issues, based on the findings of the workshops. Seminars focused on:
 - how the identified local issues are reflected and approached in the policy documents developed by CPA
 - draft policy, legislation, regulations in the e-Governance/Information Society area
- Development of Recommendations on public policies, regulations etc. amendments for the relevant public authorities based on V4 best practices and findings of seminars.

Below are described and evaluated all project activities grouped in:

1. Project events held in Chisinau, Moldova
2. Study visits in 2 Visegrad countries
3. Research Studies
4. Online visibility & Public awareness

2.1. Project events

The **objectives of the project events: workshops and seminars** were to inform and raise awareness among Moldovan local public servants, as well as different stakeholders regarding the information society development process, with an accent on the need to develop and implement e-services at the local level. Also, to present different aspects of the local electronic services by several development partners, government representatives, central authorities, academia vision.

As results of project activities, a Study Research or Report followed each project event, in order to present and analyze the achieved results, including relevant conclusions and recommendations.

In addition, after each project event were elaborated and disseminated Factsheets and Newsletters. All research studies, as well as project materials, both in Romanian and English (Factsheets, Newsletters, Press Releases and other relevant materials) are available on the project web page: www.discus.idsi.md

2.1.1. Workshop: ICT-driven local development, March 17-18 2015

On **March 17-18, 2015** the first event of the DISCUS project, workshop “ICT-driven local development” was held in Chisinau (Agenda attached in Annexes). The event was attended by more than 55 participants, representatives of different sectors: academic sector, governmental sector, Visegrad countries' diplomatic corps, civil society, mass-media.

The main goal of the event was to share the Visegrad countries experience in information society field with focus on local e-services as well as raise awareness on the importance of the local e-services by the Moldovan public servants and other relevant stakeholders.

Participants to the event opening: dr. Igor Cojocaru - director of the Information Society Development Institute, dr.hab. Veaceslav Ursachi - the representative of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Mr. Pavel Șincariuc - the head of the Department of Information Technology Policies of the Ministry of ICT, Mr. Peter Tomasek - the representative of the Slovak Embassy in Chisinau.

The key-speakers of the event were 3 experts from Visegrad countries: dr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz (Poland); Ing. Vladimir Benko (Slovakia); RN Dr. Dáteľ Vratislav (Czech Republic). The experts talked about the experience in local e-services field exemplifying both best practices and lessons learned, finally formulating a range of useful tips and recommendations.

Local key speakers: Ms. Cornelia Amihalachioae (Center for Electronic Governance)-talked about the Governance e-Transformation, the results and priorities of this process in Moldova; Ms. Oľeșea Cazacu (Joint Integrated Local Development Programme, UNDP Moldova) presented data and results of the Study on access and usage prospects of local public services on-line; Ms. Veronica Crețu (president of the Open Government Institute and member of the steering committee of the Open Government Partnership) had a presentation about Local Open Government based on ICT tools; Mr. Igor Plamadeala (Ialoveni LPA) presented the study case of the Ialoveni Rayon/district on Electronic Document Management System Implementation; Mr. Ion Cosuleanu (IDSİ) presented the new project on e-

Competence Centres “Look@IT” - a new initiative on creation of opportunities in IT for young people in rural area. (Also please see the Agenda of the event, annex 1)

The practical workshop on local e-services resulted in identification of priority (most necessary) services to be implemented at local level in Moldova (cadastral e-services, archive services, educational and health services etc.). DISCUS workshop participants showed interest regarding the subject of local electronic services and awareness on the importance of technology in all areas of public life.

In conclusion, it was agreed that Republic of Moldova has made significant progress in the digitization of public services at the central level. The success of these activities creates promising prerequisites for the digitisation of the local public services, by providing access to registries and databases of central authorities, by transfer of experience, by adapting existing technical solutions to the specific local context.

However, at the moment, a consolidated vision on local public services that could be digitized, as well as future institutional framework, to ensure their digitization, doesn't exist.

Based on the experience of Visegrad countries, it can be ascertained that the digitization of local services was initiated, primarily based on the degree of demand for these services, while the informational support relies primarily on centralized resources. The legal-normative framework has a key role in the digitization of local public services, in the absence thereof, the services that could be provided in electronic form become mainly information services for the citizens. An importing role in facilitating the digitization of public services was played by the standardization of public services, which allowed increasing their accessibility and reducing costs for development and implementation of a proper information infrastructure. The digitization of local public services in Visegrad countries became possible due to extensive digital literacy campaigns of the population, especially the elderly.

Clearing the digital divide between urban and rural environments is a necessary condition for successful implementation of digital services provided by local authorities.

Analysis of the workshop results leads to the following **conclusions**:

1. In the Republic of Moldova the process of local public services digitization is at the initial stage, the few existing attempts refer mostly to the use of ICT for disseminating information, pertaining to the activity of local public administration and informing citizens.
2. One of the priorities in the digitization of local public services should be their prioritization depending on the level of demand and identification of those public services, which when digitised would have significant social and economic effects.
3. It is necessary to perform a detailed inventory and a clear delineation of public services provided by local authorities and those provided by the central government, when the local authority only plays the role of agent/operator providing the service.
4. A unique public policy is needed for digitizing local public services. This policy should address all aspects of this process: normative-legal, institutional, technical, and organizational.
5. The digitization of local public services should be started with the digitization of all processes within local authorities themselves.
6. Digitisation of local public services requires standard technological solutions. The development of such technological solutions is the responsibility of the central government.

Analysis of the questionnaires completed (anonymously) by about 30 participants, proves that the vast majority was satisfied with the event (see the figure below):

Related to questions 4 “**What did you find most useful?**” - most of the answers referred to the presentations of experts from Visegrad countries and their recommendations. Similarly, many mentioned the practical exercise which referred to the identification of local services that should be digitized.

The question “If this workshop were offered again, would you recommend it to a colleague?” received 27 affirmative answers and 0 negative.

Overall, 63% of participants stated their expectations from the event were met fully, partially - 37% and "not at all" – 0 (see the figure below).

More detailed information may be found in the 1st Research Study: **Recommendation on implementation of relevant Information System for Local Authorities (March - April 2015)**.

The Newsletter on Workshop is available at <http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Newsletter-2-March-2015>

The Factsheet on the Workshop is attached (Annex 2) and can be accessed on <http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-2-eng>

2.1.2. Scientific seminar: ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations) May 26-27, 2015

The second event of the DISCUS project was organised on **May 26-27, 2015** in Chisinau. The scientific seminar was entitled “**ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations)**” (Agenda provided in the Annex 1).

The main goal of the Seminar was to share the experience of Visegrad countries in the field of information society with a focus on legal regulations in the field of electronic services, including local services and taking into consideration V4 best practices in this area by the Moldavian officials, researchers and national policy makers. The objective of the seminar was to discuss the problems and identify possible solutions regarding legal regulations for local electronic services in Moldova.

The seminar brought about the valuable input information from representatives of local and central public authorities of Moldova on the one hand, and from the V4 countries experts on the other hand. The event was attended by approx. 50 specialists in various areas: local public servants, representatives of academic sector, central government, civil society, national experts and international experts from Visegrad countries.

The seminar was opened by the representative of the [Academy of Sciences](#) - Dr.hab. Veaceslav Ursachi coordinator of Engineering Sciences and Technology Section of ASM.

With a word of greeting came the director of [Information Society Development Institute](#) - Dr. Igor Cojocaru and Deputy Head of the Department of Information Technology Policies, [Ministry of Information and Communication Technology](#) - Andrei Cușcă.

Professor, dr.hab. Anatol Gremalschi, Program director at Public Policy Institute presented the study conducted by the DISCUS experts based on the Ist DISCUS workshop from 17-18 March, which had the topic: ICT-driven local development.

Andrei Cușcă, Deputy Head of the Department of Information Technology Policies, [Ministry of ICT](#) has presented the National Strategy "Digital Moldova 2020" - the basic policy document on development of information society in Moldova.

Igor Cernei, specialist in information technologies, Orhei City Hall presented the case study: Center for Information and Services of Orhei City Hall and the Geographic Information System Orhei. Petru Culeac, Community Mobilization Consultant, [USAID Local Government Support Project in Moldova](#) talked about Development and institutionalization of effective communication with citizens instruments (1.0 WebAPL platform).

The key-speakers of the event were 3 experts from Visegrad countries. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz from Poland presented useful information and advices for ICT strategic planning by local authorities. Vladimir Benko, Slovakia spoke about the model of open self-government of Presov – systematic and effective building of info services and on the second day of the seminar presented ICT tools for environmental management at local level, issuing several recommendations to Moldova. Vratislav Datel (Czech Republic) talked about legislation and technical standards in Public Administration.

Eduard Fricățel, legal consultant and Vlad Manoil, specialist of the Center for Electronic Governance presented the legal framework for Governance Agenda eTransformation, respectively eGovernment platforms implemented for central public authorities and available for reuse by local authorities. The event ended with a

communication about interoperability as an opportunity to modernize local services presented by PhD Mihai Grecu, Head of Laboratory at the Information Society Development Institute.

To implement on-line service delivery at the local level, several participants mentioned the necessity to focus on needs. As a priority, they relate to: (i) providing equipment and computers, (ii) developing procurement databases and electronic data processing programs, (iii) data processing of archive records accumulated in City Halls.

In addition to supplying equipment and technical facilities needed at the local level, there is an urgent need to reduce the number of certificates and documents required for issuing different acts.

Specialists within LPA reform implementation highlighted the need to digitize public services throughout the territory of the country, by creating *a single common system of service provision*. But first it is necessary to ensure service functionality, both technically and in terms of human resources. However, it may be emphasized and stated that local authorities are to promote and actively explore new opportunities for public services in electronic mode, including the launch of local pilot services, such as requesting and obtaining notification of payment of taxes, the certificate on place of residence, certificate about family, the extract from the Land Registry.

LPAs are also faced with a number of problems related particularly to the current organization, and especially to the insufficiency of resources for the implementation of ICT solutions, such as¹:

- the lack of registries in hard copy of the services provided, and the lack of record keeping of services, respectively;
- insufficient resources (for e.g. cars, funds for covering the telephone costs, in some cases, the computers used are old and need to be replaced);
- the risk of discontinuing some services which are provided only by one person, whose absence makes it impossible to further provide them;
- low storage security of documents/information (for example, there is no fire alarm system for the hard copy archives in the LPA offices);
- insufficient licensed programs, lack of automated programs for documents handling;
- limited communication at the level of electronic data exchange between LPAs, DSs, and other local actors, the lack of corporative e-mail addresses.

The participants to the Seminar mainly confirmed the above-mentioned issues and underlined a range of issues in implementation of e-services on local level, such as:

- lack of political will
- lack of information campaigns for the citizen and of training for civil servants in rural areas;
- documents duplication;
- lack of pilot projects from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages which could be undertaken for multiplication in other localities;

¹ Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center
<http://www.descentralizare.gov.md/lib.php?l=en&idc=446&t=/DRAFTS-IN-DISCUSSION/Concept-of-Citizen-Information-and-Service-Center>

- resistance to change;
- lack of experts group who would consult and support local authorities in e-services implementation;
- lack of a partnership network (central government, local, civil society, business etc.)
- local authorities are the main/biggest data providers, but at the same time they do not have access to these data
- necessity of a stocktaking of all public authorities possessions (in terms of ICT, information systems etc.)
- Moldova has good strategies but there is a lack of finance for a better implementation of all plans, documents.

DISCUS - scientific seminar participants showed interest in the subject of e-services at the local level, focusing on legal regulations, acknowledging the importance of technology in all areas of public life.

According to the final evaluation questionnaires completed by participants of the seminar from May 26-27, the majority were very satisfied or satisfied with the organization of the event. 100% of participants would recommend the seminar to colleagues for participation.

What did you find most useful? (*Some of the participants' answers, more of them were repeated*)

1. LPA opinions
2. Discussions, exchange of experience
3. Best practice of LPA in Moldova and the Visegrad countries
4. Cooperation of CPA and LPA from V4 countries
5. The programs that have been presented for a possible deployment
6. Experience of city Orhei, Moldova and Poland, the vision of Visegrad experts on the computerization of LPA in the Republic of Moldova
7. The example of the implemented project in Orhei
8. Exchange of experience, establish the opportunities for future cooperation

9. Good practice of Orhei participant shared with the participants
10. The possibilities of implementing electronic management in LPA of I level
11. Programs presentations and foreign partners practices
12. The use of e-services experience from Orhei
13. We are on the right way with innovation, but we must keep working on the legislative side
14. The experience of other states
15. The communication between participants after the presentations
16. The proposal and acceptance of our districts to implement information systems

More detailed information can be find in the Research Study **Recommendations on Public Policies, Regulations/ Amendments for the relevant Public Authorities from the Republic of Moldova (June – July 2015)**

The Newsletter on seminar can be accessed at
<http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Newsletter-3-June-2015>

The Factsheet on the seminar is attached (Annex 2) and can be accessed on:
<http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-3-eng>

2.1.3. Workshop: Electronic Local Public Services, September 22-23 2015

The second workshop: **Electronic Local Public Services**, took place on **September 22-23**, in Chisinau. The event was attended by 55 participants, including representatives of 36 town/villages halls from Moldova, **among them 19 mayors, 2 deputy mayors, 5 secretaries of the local councils and 10 specialists of LPA coming from 27 villages, 6 towns and 14 rayons** of Moldova. Also at the event have participated representatives of academic sector, central government, civil society, national experts and international experts from Visegrad countries.

The workshop had a practical character, the working teams were coordinated by 4 experts: 3 from Visegrad countries – Poland, Slovakia and Czech Republic; and the national expert from Moldova. The discussions focused on the Action plan for implementation of local electronic services. The workshop lasted one and a half days, participants having the possibility for networking, brainstorming of ideas and exchange of experience.

The **main goal** of the event was to develop action plans by the moldovan local public servants under the guidance of Visegrad experts.

The **objective of the workshop** was to inform and raise awareness among moldovan local public servants on the need to develop and implement action plans for local electronic services, as well as to train practical skills of participants in planning and discussing an action plan concept.

The welcome speeches were delivered by dr. Igor Cojocaru – director of Information Society Development Institute, Andrei Cușcă – deputy head of the Department of IT policies of the [Ministry of ICT](#), dr.hab. Veaceslav Ursachi – coordinator of the Department of Engineering and Technological Sciences of the ASM, c.m. Constantin Gaidric – [Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences of ASM](#).

Professor, dr.hab. Anatol Gremalschi, program director at Institute of Public Policies

made a presentation of the research study compiled by DISCUS experts, based on the findings of the scientific seminar held on May 26-27, 2015 focused on [ICT solutions for local services \(legal regulations\)](#).

Another presentation during the event was focused on the study visit in Poland (July 5-10, 2015). The participants at the study visit made a presentation, sharing the gained experience and the results of the study visit. Igor Cernei, from Orhei mentioned the Geospatial System, for which they plan to increase the implementation areas of the system (roads, road traffic, public maps) and to identify instruments for a more efficient management of the system (geographical reference points, meteorological sensors, automated information monitors), following the model seen in Poland. They also start planning the electronic circuit of documents, including such functionalities as documents execution recording, managing the document status, system structure, the use of structuring certificates, use of digital signatures. Lilia Golovatic from com. Sarata Veche planned to improve the communication between LPA and citizens through IT tools, based on models from Poland – SMS text, on-line streamed meetings, good/interactive web pages of the LPA. In addition, she realised the importance of trainings and seminars on IT topic.

Ion Cosuleanu, researcher at IDSI presented a set of recommendations on drawing up a plan of action for implementation of local electronic services. Based on the recommendations, the working teams (consisting of mayors, deputy mayors, secretaries of local councils and specialists) worked on developing action plans for implementation of local services, considered of high priority and common to several localities (e.g. issuance of certificates, cadastral extracts etc.).

The teams presented and evaluated their proposals based on the criteria explained by prof. Anatol Gremalschi, DISCUS project national expert:

- eligibility (the service you propose for digitization falls within your city hall competences?)
- relevance (do the citizens really need this service?)
- effectiveness (will it achieve its purpose of digitization?)
- efficiency (which will be the benefits? will they cover the cost of digitization?)
- durability.

Short analysis of the participant's presentations/ideas presented during the workshop from September

First of all it has to be stressed that the main goal of work in groups during September workshop was to envisage the participants the problems that arise during the implementation of e-service. This goal was accomplished as participants pointed out most important aspects that have to be taken care of.

It has to be stressed however that most of the problems regarding implementation of IT systems are common. That is why it is important to use common methodologies and standards. This enables to focus the attention to the specific problems. Those issues usually are no more than 5% of the project – however they may jeopardize the whole initiative.

In brief: it is no use to push on the door that is already open.

Returning to the work groups, one very important conclusion arises: the cornerstone of any e-service is proper website. Analysis made during workshop pointed out that few LPA in Moldova do not have any kind of website. In other cases, there are some problems of existing web pages: often they are not properly maintained, sometimes out of date or use awkward layout.

Therefore, it seems that two most important tasks to be performed are:

- Implementation of website in LPA which lack such a device,
- Standardization of existing portals.

Conclusions of the event:

1. In the Republic of Moldova the process of local public services digitization is at the initial stage, the few existing attempts refer mostly to the use of ICT for disseminating information, pertaining to the activity of local public administration and informing citizens.

2. One of the priorities in the digitization of local public services should be their prioritization depending on the level of demand and identification of those public services, which when digitised would have significant social and economic effects.

3. It is necessary to perform a detailed inventory and a clear delineation of public services provided by local authorities and those provided by the central government, when the local authority only plays the role of agent/operator providing the service.

4. A unique public policy is needed for digitizing local public services. This policy should address all aspects of this process: normative-legal, institutional, technical, organizational.

5. The digitization of local public services should be started with the digitization of all processes within local authorities themselves.

6. Digitisation of local public services requires standard technological solutions. The development of such technological solutions is the responsibility of the central government.

The participants at the event, were generally satisfied with the overall organization of the workshop, discussed issues and experts performance. According to questionnaire results, 61% of the participants were most satisfied and 39% - satisfied with the event (see below).

Some of the participants' comments:

- In general, the workshop was very well organized and the accents were put on the most sensitive issues.

- Organized at the highest possible level.
- Logical timing of the issues for discussion at all levels, involving the majority of participants
- It was as expected (very good).
- The subjects discussed are topical and it is necessary to apply information service and provision of electronic services in LPAs.
- These seminars should be carried out in regions where such electronic services were implemented.
- A seminar well organized and with all issues covered.
- Talks were organized so that participants find answers to their questions, it's a good opportunity to exchange ideas and experiences.
- It was a useful workshop, with an important topic. It is necessary to develop a national portal of public services.
- In general the organization was good, useful information, teamwork was a positive aspect.
- All subjects are necessary, to continue the work and develop our villages.

More detailed information can be found in the document: Research Study nr. 3 **Recommendations on Local Public E-Services to be Developed (September – November 2015)**

The Newsletter nr. 5 can be accessed at: <http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Newsletter-5-september-2015>

The Factsheet on the Workshop is attached (Annex 2) and can be accessed on: <http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-5-eng>

2.1.4. Seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (practical aspects), November 24-25 2015

The seminar was attended by approx. **120 people**, including 15 mayors, 20 deputy mayors, secretaries of local/district councils, 20 representatives of libraries, schools/colleges/universities, as well as several experts from local public authorities of Ist and IInd level from Moldova.

The event was attended by **Acad. Ion Tighineanu, senior vice president of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova; Sergiu Ceaus, Deputy Secretary General of the Government; Andrei Cusca, Ministry of Information Technology and Communications; Dr. Veaceslav Ursachi, head of the Engineering and Technology Sciences Department of ASM**. According to evaluation questionnaires full filled by participants at the event, they appreciated the presence and presentations of the government representatives and Academy of Sciences of Moldova. Their messages have conferred more trust to all participants that all stakeholders of the information society development process are interested and take into account the local problems. In a way, this was a message of encouraging for mayors, local specialists that they are supported by the central decision makers.

The seminar started with the presentation of practical issues regarding the protection of personal data, carried out by two experts from the National Center for Personal Data

Protection. This subject was practically new for LPAs, even they had the legal duty to register the authority as holder of personal data. Based on the final evaluation questionnaire, this subject was appreciated by the participants as one of the most useful, presented during the event.

The representatives of the State Chancellery presented the funding instruments from external sources for LPAs. Therefore, the local servants could find out several external funds that can finance their projects.

Experts from e-Government Center demonstrated reusable electronic government services. There was presented the national e-service portal: www.servicii.gov.md, and the e-services that can be reused at the local level. Once again was shown what have been done until now at the central level and what can teach local administration from this experience.

Because during first 3 events of the DISCUS project organized in Chisinau, one of the problems of the IT at local level was identified and discussed was the web pages of the LPAs done on foreign domain. In this propose, was invited the administrator of SE MoldData - Dorian Bodi. He spoke about the ".MD" domain for LPAs: penetrability, challenges and reality. Were discussed the issues of local authorities with the development of web pages, maintenance of official emails, cyber security.

Project manager and IT consultant for UNDP – Olesea Cazacu and Eugen Platitu presented IT instruments for LPAs, developed within the projects implemented by UNDP Moldova. They announced about the Document Management IT system development as a tool for LPAs from Moldova. Novateca program results were presented and were announced the next activities within the program as opportunities for local, rural libraries as well as for LPAs that manage with local libraries; including IT opportunities.

Experts from the Visegrad countries: Poland, Slovakia, the Czech Republic came up with several suggestions for implementation of e-services at the local level, by sharing the experiences from their respective countries. Participants had opportunities, during the event, to ask questions about Visegrad experience especially in rural areas.

During the event were presented the results of the study visit in Slovakia from October 5-9. The participants at the study visit shared their opinions and good examples acquired during discussions with specialists from Slovakia and presented their future actions based on thinks learned following the visit. For e.g., Cristina Grajdieru – PR Specialist, Public Administration Department, District Council Singerei, has underlined 3 things that inspired her:

- Making use of the European funds for implementation of project with socio-economic impact;

- Applying the vast potential of ICTs in the public sector;

- Integration of disabled people in society.

As a result of the study visit to Slovakia, Cristina proposed the following:

- Information and Services Delivery Center from Singerey Town Hall to be used for electronic services, such as issuing various certificates;

- the Town Halls from the district should develop their own webpages, using the national domain name “.MD” (at the moment only 8 Town Halls out of 26 have a webpage).

A topic of interest for local government representatives was the presentation focused on "Household Register. Conceptual Approach" delivered by Mihai Grecu - Information Society Development Institute. Even until now have been started a lot of initiatives at central

level to find a IT solution for this problem, today there is no concrete result and LPAs continue to issue and keep a lot of documents on papers.

ISDI Director, Dr. Igor Cojocaru presented innovative services of ISDI, which could be opportunities for LPAs, services like virtual tour, network management, information systems development, web development etc.

Some of results of the Evaluation questionnaires of the event show that the majority of participants were most satisfied with the organization of the event, as well as the style and level of communication between organizers and participants (see the figure below).

More detailed information can be found in the document: [Research Study Recommendations on action plan for implementation of local e-services \(November-December 2015\)](#)

The Newsletter nr. 7 can be accessed at: <http://discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-7-eng>

The Factsheet on the seminar is attached (Annex 2) and can be accessed at <http://discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-7-eng>

Besides the planned activities within the DISCUS project, were organized 2 extra events. In June and in December were organized 2 round tables focused on the national digital content, recognized as a national priority of Moldova.

Additional Project events

2.1.5. Round Table: Valorisation of the national scientific heritage through digital content, June 5, 2015

On 5 June 2015 the Information Society Development Institute (ISDI) in partnership with the State University of Moldova (USM) organized a round table **Valorisation of the national scientific heritage through digital content**.

The round table was organized in the context of increased focus on transparency, access and development of new tools for scientific collaboration, dissemination of scientific information and creating new facilities for access to scientific knowledge.

The event was a joint effort of IDSI's institutional project „Pilot Platform for ensuring quality evaluation and visualization of digital scientific content in Moldova” and DISCUS project (IVF – contract nr. 21470018). Its aim was to present the innovative results and applied research projects in areas related to digitizing, documenting, archiving and capitalization of the scientific heritage of the Republic of Moldova.

The event was attended by around 70 people, including representatives of the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications, Ministry of Culture, directors and representatives of libraries, both from Moldova and Romania, as well as others interested in the topic.

The event began with a **discussion session focused on digital content policies and strategies in Moldova**, moderating by **dr. hab. Nelly Turcan**. A welcome speech was delivered by **dr., assoc. prof. Angela Niculița**, Vice-Rector for International Relations of the SUM, **Vitalie Tarlev**, Deputy Minister of Information Technology and Communications, **dr. Igor Sarov**, Deputy Minister of Culture and **dr. Lydia Kulikovski** from Novateca Program. Director of the Information Society Development Institute, **dr. Igor Cojocar** presented an **analysis of national policies on digital content creation until 2020**.

Mr. Tiganas Ion, Deputy Director of the State Agency for Intellectual Property of the Republic of Moldova (AGEPI) focused on copyright and AGEPI contribution to unlocking scientific heritage through digital content, followed by a series of discussions and debates on the digital market in Moldova, digital scientific content, copyright on scientific content, digitized content, national scientific heritage etc.

The second part of the event continued with a **session of presentations on the best practices for digitizing, creating and using digital content**.

Ms. Diana Lupușor, Head of digitization department, [National Library of Moldova](#) spoke about trends and developments in digitization of cultural heritage and the experience of the National Digital Library Moldavia. The Coordinator of the scientific journal *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae* of the SUM, Ceban Lilia, presented the journal as a platform for promotion of scientific results. **Ms. Tatiana Bulmaga**, Head of department for scientific results protection and exploitation of the SUM, presented the experience of the State University of Moldova in combating plagiarism and copyright protection. The head of "Ethnic minorities" Unit at the Cultural Heritage Institute of the Academy of Sciences, **dr. Ion Duminica**, focused on the methods, tools and techniques to digitize phonograms, field data and written ethnographic information. Finally **Ms. Diana Ghiorghies**, Country Manager at [Quito Romania](#) presented the Eldorado project - online access to digitized documents from the librarians' collections.

More information and presentations of the event available on <http://discus.idsi.md/en/round-table-capitalization-of-national-scientific-heritage-through-digital-content> & <http://www.discus.idsi.md/ro/masa-rotunda-patrimoniul-stiintific-5-iunie-2015-event>

2.1.6. Round table: National Digital Scientific Content for Public Access, December 9, 2015

On 9 December 2015 Information Society Development Institute organized a **round table** entitled: **Scientific journals - a catalyst for increasing the quality and visibility of digital scientific content**.

The event was attended by approx. **80 representatives** of the editorial boards of Moldovan scientific journals, researchers from the institutions of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova. The round table, as part of the DISCUS project (International Visegrad Fund - nr. 21470018), was streamed online and watched by approx. 100 users.

The purpose of the round table was to discuss digital scientific content and ways to enhance its quality and visibility. According to the joint decision of Supreme Council for Science and Technological Development and National Council for Accreditation and Attestation (nr.147 of 06/25/2015), starting January 1, 2016 all scientific journals from Moldova must be registered in the [National Bibliometric Tool \(IBN\)](#). Thus, during the event was presented the database National Bibliometric Tool, implemented and developed by ISDI, as a tool to assist the editorial boards.

In order to implement the Government Decision nr. 920 of 11.7.2014 on Research and Development Strategy of Moldova until 2020 and the Government Decision nr. 857 of 31.10.2013 on the National Strategy for Information Society Development "Digital Moldova 2020", as well as the new Regulations regarding the evaluation, classification and monitoring of scientific journals, approved on 25.06.2015, the Academy of Sciences of Moldova is to make an inventory of the existing digital scientific content and perform a needs assessment, for the digitization of the national scientific content. The information and data owned by science and innovation institutions are valuable information resources, are to be digitized, stored and disseminated, in order to be available for the general public.

In this regard, the National Bibliometric Tool is a scientific electronic library which stores, classifies and measures public data regarding scientific publications of researchers from Moldova.

The **National Bibliometric Tool** is a unique national database, that has already gathered about 40 thousand publications from accredited national scientific journals. IBN is visited annually by over 20 thousand visitors from 97 countries.

More information on <http://www.discus.idsi.md/ro/masa-rotunda-continut-digital-9-12-15-event> & <http://discus.idsi.md/en/round-table-national-digital-scientific-content>

2.2. Study Visits

The purpose of the study visits organized within the DISCUS project during 2015 was the exchange of experience, the transfer of best practices from Visegrad countries (Poland and Slovakia) to the Republic of Moldova, establishing contacts and fostering collaboration on Information Society field (focusing on local electronic services). These activities addressed mainly local public servants from Moldova, who were selected based on application forms. The main criteria of the selection were: job position and experience in public sphere; the level of understanding of e-services concept/ e-Transformation process; the purpose of their participation; and activities planned after returning from the study visit.

After each study visit, all participants discussed the lessons learnt during the visit, good examples/experiences which had inspired them and what do they plan to apply within their home institution. Following each study visit were elaborated and disseminated electronic Factsheets and Newsletters (Romanian and English versions), available on the project web page.

2.2.1. Study visit in Poland

On **July 6-10, 2015**, was organised a study visit in Poland. A team of 5 persons from Moldova visited several cities from Poland:

1. **Anastasia Ștefanița** - [Information Society Development Institute](#), responsible for international relations
2. **Igor Plamădeală** - [Ialoveni District Council](#), Head of Public Administration Section
3. **Lilia Golovatic** - village hall [Sărata Veche](#), Specialist in writing and implementing projects
4. **Igor Cernei** - [City Hall](#) Orhei, IT Specialist
5. **Cristina Smolenschi** - [City Hall Călărași](#), Specialist in management of public property

The **purpose of the study visit** was the exchange of experience, the transfer of best practices from Poland to Moldova, establishing contacts and fostering collaboration on Information Society field (focusing on local electronic services). The main objective of these activities within the DISCUS project is observing the best Polish practices by Moldovan servants and assimilation of lessons learned by Polish local authorities in the local electronic services field.

The study visit was organized by [ISDI](#) in collaboration with the project partner from Poland - [Information Society Development Foundation](#).

The **study tour program** was an active one, comprising several public institutions, municipalities and meetings with specialists in various fields. (Please see the agenda at annex 1). Thus, on the first day of the visit, the participants visited the [Information Society Development Foundation \(FRSI\)](#) headquarters in Warsaw, where they met with **Rafal Kramza** - the president of the foundation. The participants became acquainted with programs and projects of FRSI in [development libraries](#) in Poland (2009-2015). Then followed the presentation of Mr. Paul Shmayda, **GEOPOLIS**, on municipal management - solution "smart city", Geographic Information System (GIS).

On Tuesday, the participants visited the [Piotrkow Trybunalski](#) city. They realized a tour in [several public authorities](#), departments that provide public services. There were presented and analysed: document management systems; Piotrkow e-learning platform; GIS; operation "profiles of confidence" for communicating with the public authorities; Information Center. Also, the **public library of Piotrkow** was visited, which has new IT tools to communicate with readers and for book fund management.

On the third day of the visit, the team was at the [Ministry of Justice in Poland](#), where they visited the IT department and courts records/registers. In the second part of the day they visited the [City Hall of Zielonka](#). Besides [meeting with the mayor](#), participants had the opportunity to talk to experts in ICT field. There were presented methods/tools of

communication with citizens: SMS; e-mail; on-line broadcasts of meetings; web page of public documents etc.

On Thursday, the group went to **Cracow** where they had meetings in the [Central Office of Malopolska Voivodship](#). In discussions with various specialists, Moldovan officials were able to learn more about video communication system of the institution with citizens; about e-learning system; Virtual museums in the region; electronic document management systems etc.

On Friday, were held **an assessment meeting** of the study visit. Participants rated each activity and underlined the usefulness of discussions with various specialists. According to the evaluation questionnaires, each participant of the study visit managed to acquire some successful practices of Poland that they plan to implement in towns/ villages where they come from. In addition to theoretical knowledge, the participants at the study visit had the opportunity to talk directly with experts who have implemented concrete systems or even to test directly some IT tools.

The results of the study visit in Poland were presented during the **Workshop: Electronic Local Public Services, from September 22-23 2015** (please see more details above, at chapter about the workshop).

The newsletter on study visit is available on

<http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Newsletter-4-July-2015>

The factsheet with information on Study visit attached and available at:

<http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-4-eng>

2.2.2. Study visit in Slovakia

During **October 5-9, 2015** a team of **5 persons from Moldova** participated at a **study visit in Slovakia**. The group consisted of **3 public local servants** ([Orhei](#), [Sîngerei](#), [Hîncești](#)) and **2 researchers** from the **Information Society Development Institute**.

During the study tour, the group visited **4 localities** (**Bratislava, Nitra, Viglas, Banska Bystrica**), **15 institutions**: ministries, state agencies, town halls, IT companies, S&T centres, museums, libraries, NGOs. Were presented approx. **20 presentations**, including presentations of e-services, IT systems, educational soft etc. (Please see the agenda at annex 1).

Participants had the opportunity to discuss directly with IT specialists, heads of departments, responsible for IT project implementation; they had shared their experience and established new contacts for future ideas exchange and collaborations.

The Moldovan group could observe how are organised public e-services using the national portal www.slovensko.sk, functionalities of electronic systems in R&D field, they could understand the new concept of technologized museum, interactive library and GIS systems.

The participants at the study tour remained with positive impressions, but also with concrete ideas how they can implement local e-services, to improve their initiated systems or to increase the effectiveness of communication between citizens and administration.

The purpose of the study visit was the exchange of experience, the transfer of best practices from Slovakia to Moldova, establishing contacts and fostering collaboration on Information Society field (focusing on local electronic services). The main objective of these

activities within the DISCUS project was observing the best Slovak practices by Moldovan servants and assimilation of lessons learned by Slovak local authorities in the local electronic services field.

Based on **evaluation** questionnaires:

Participants mentioned 2-3 of the most valuable issues they have learned during the study visit	In participants' opinion, the following aspects in the activity of their institution could be improved thanks to the study visit:
GIS implementing advice National portal of services implementation Smart Zone organization	More various services for citizens, specially more GIS services
Smart Zones Database of Cities E-services for citizens	Smart Zone for tourists Information Centre for citizens Development concept of local e-strategy
S&T systems / R& D a good collaboration between private companies (GAMO e.g.) and cultural/education institutions (museum, universities) with IT projects.	R&D e-systems IT management New modules on web page
The big importance of interoperability between systems The importance of collaboration with Government in developing application for citizens Moldova should not make the same mistakes that other countries did	To develop new applications for citizens. To improve the existing applications.
The e-services presented by the Ministry of Labour are a good example for Moldova The contact with people is very important and providing information to citizens	The e-services presented in State Scientific Library The model of websites

The results of the study visit in Slovakia were presented during the **Seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (practical aspects), from November 24-25 2015** (please see more details above, the chapter about the seminar).

More information and Participants presentations can be found at <http://discus.idsi.md/en/study-visit-Slovakia>

The newsletter on study visit can be accessed on http://www.discus.idsi.md/sites/default/files/NewsLetter_6-Eng.pdf

The Factsheet on Study visit in Slovakia is attached and can be accessed on: <http://www.discus.idsi.md/en/Factsheet-6-eng>

2.3. Research studies

During the project implementation period, following each of the 4 planned events (2 workshops and 2 seminars), were developed a series of research studies, as follows:

- Recommendation on implementation of relevant Information System for Local Authorities (*March - April 2015*);

- Recommendations on Public Policies, Regulations/ Amendments for the relevant Public Authorities from the Republic of Moldova (*June – July 2015*);
- Recommendations on Local Public E-Services to be Developed (*September – November 2015*);
- Recommendations on action plan for implementation of local e-services (*November – December 2015*).

The group of experts involved in studies elaboration includes:

- **Visegrad experts:**
RN Dr. Vratislav Datel - Expert, Czech Republic
Dr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz - Expert, Poland
Ing. Vladimir Benko - Expert, Slovakia
- **National expert, Moldova:**
Dr. hab. Anatol Gremalschi – The Public Policies Institute, Chişinău
- **Support team:**
Dr. Igor Cojocaru - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău
Ion Coşuleanu - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău
Anastasia Ştefaniţa - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău

2.3.1. Recommendation on implementation of relevant Information System for Local Authorities (March - April 2015)

The goal of this study is to present the results of the first project event – workshop: ICT-driven local development, held in Chisinau on March 17-18, 2015. The objective of the study is to analyse the lessons learned by the participating countries (Visegrad group and Moldova) and to develop a set of recommendations, which will enable the digitisation of services delivered to citizens by the local public authorities. Within the study are presented the each Visegrad country experience in ICT driven local development and best practices best practices relevant to be approached by Moldova, including lessons learnt. Based on the workshop findings the experts formulated concrete recommendations on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities from Moldova.

2.3.2. Recommendations on Public Policies, Regulations/ Amendments for the relevant Public Authorities from the Republic of Moldova (June – July 2015)

The goal of the study is to present the results of the seminar focused on legal regulations in the field of the information society of Moldova, from May 26-27. The research presents a comprehensive analysis of the problems and identifies possible solutions regarding legal regulations for local electronic services in Moldova, taking into consideration V4 best practices in this area by the Moldavian officials, researchers and national policy makers.

The materials of the research study are sometimes beyond the Seminar discussions, to provide additional information on EU, V4 countries experience, as well as on the state of the art on discussed issues in the Republic of Moldova. In the State of the Art chapter, the

information on the Republic of Moldova administrative structure is provided in order to help V4 experts to deliver more focused recommendations to actions to be undertaken by the country, in transposition of the EU and V4 countries experience.

A special chapter is devoted to Visegrad countries experience on ICT solutions for local services (with a focus on experience in legal regulations field) and best practices relevant to be approached by Moldova. The chapter on Lessons learnt provides ICT solutions for local services, focused on the experience of the Czech Republic, Slovakia and Poland in legal regulations field.

2.3.3. Recommendations on Local Public E-Services to be Developed (September – November 2015)

The main goal of this research study is to present the results of the workshop from September 22-23, on Electronic Local Public Services. Firstly is made a short analysis of the event. The chapter 2 presents general notions about public services. After general definitions of public services, an analysis of the legal framework for public services in Moldova is presented, with an accent on local services. The chapter 4: e-services presents the concept of services based on ICT, the principles, criteria for selection, how to plan a n e-service at local level. The next paragraph is about actual situation of e-services in Moldova, followed by some practical tips. Visegrad experts formulated several comments and recommendations based on first 3 DISCUS events.

2.3.4. Recommendations on action plan for implementation of local e-services (November – December 2015)

The main goal of this research study is to present the results of the seminar from November on ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues). Firstly is made a short analysis of the event and the impact of the DISCUS seminar is presented. An analysis of the actual relevant problems identified during the seminar was performed: personal data protection; use of national domain .md; financial opportunities for LPAs from Moldova. Following the general notions on e-services, the levels of e-service are presented. There pre-conditions before writing action plan for e-services are specified, which should be taken into consideration by the LPA. For a better understanding, a set of complex analyses are presented: SWOT; Data, Competencies, Needs, Infrastructure and IT analysis. There is a special chapter dedicated to the Action Plan for e-services development, which describes what an action plan is, how it looks and is given a general template of the action plan for e-service implementation. Within the research study, there is a questionnaire for LPAs from the Republic of Moldova, proposed by the Visegrad and Moldovan experts, based on the findings of the seminar (as well as all project events during 2015).

General conclusions on Research Studies

All research studies of the project are linked among them and each study represents a logical continuation of the previous one. All research studies were distributed to participants during the project events in two languages: English (the language in which the documents

were written by the experts) and in Romanian (translated from original English version, particularly with the goal to be better understood by Moldovan participants at DISCUS events and to ensure a better dissemination and applicability by the project beneficiaries). In addition, all research studies are published on the project web page: <http://discus.idsi.md/en/reports> and can be freely accessed in English and Romanian versions.

2.3.5. Research studies conclusions and consolidated recommendations

1. To succeed in implementation of ICT based services at the local level the country-wide approach is necessary to be applied.
2. The best practices from V4 countries provided in the present paper have to be additionally analysed through already planned actions in the existing documents in the field of Information Society development in the Republic of Moldova.
3. The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016², approved by Government Decision on 25 June 2014 is one of the most important documents in approximation of legal framework on Information Society and ICT based services to those of the EU.
4. The second relevant document is the Public Services Reform Program approved by the Government and recently updated³ containing provisions at the extent that they concern ICT based local public services, is to be followed.
5. The third document to be followed is the Briefing Book from Development Partners (January, 2015)⁴
6. The most recent document is the Government of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018 (see the relevant Excerpt in the Annex 5)
7. The documents to be developed recommended by V4 experts are partially covered by the Program and by the National Action Plan.
8. It is suggested to have a coordinated approach for legal decrees in the area of informatics on local level in the whole country, as much as possible.
9. The basic principles must be set equally for the whole country. The specific differences can be adopted on the local level but a research should be carried out when creating such documents, to examine the similar situations in other local governments. If that is the case, the law content should be harmonized across the whole local level. The <http://www.actelocale.md/> platform shall be used for ensuring the proposed approach and for transparency of local authorities.
10. Such practice will bring benefits for citizens and entrepreneurs. It will also bring advantages for the public sector, at least for the exchange of data and for statistical comparisons.
11. For the approval process of legal decrees on national level is advisable to use the participation approach (already established through the portal www.particip.gov.md).
12. Access to basic registers: Population Register, Register of Legal Entities, Addresses Register has to be ensured for all public authorities according to legal provisions.
13. Balanced approach between respecting protection of personal data and access to necessary data for effective and efficient functionality of ICT based services by public authorities.

² Approved by Government Decision on 25 June 2014

³ Government Decision nr.198 of 23.04.2015

⁴ Briefing Book from development partners of Moldova

<http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/moldova/publication/briefing-book>

14. It is quite useful to buy / provide key technology at central / regional level. This leads to massive cost reductions.⁵
15. The “Paperless Government” initiative in Moldova was planned to be implemented, so as from the beginning of 2014 the offices of hundreds of public officials working in ministries, agencies and departments had to be paper free. However, in spite of the fact that SIGEDIA Documents Management System was piloted in 9 ministries, only the Ministry of Education declared paperless document management inside the institution implemented as from April, 2015.
16. It is necessary to analyse and understand the implementation problem of SIGEDIA and find alternatives in Document Management System Implementation. This is an issue that can be discussed on the DISCUS platform.
17. Deployment of the common technology should be put on the market to enable smaller local companies to benefit.
18. It is important to have a separate way to remunerate IT staff.
19. It is good to include IT procurement specifics in Public Procurement Laws:
 - a. Ability to take the aspects like risk, service and experience into account,
 - b. Ability to include expertise in the tenders.
20. It is very important to standardize procedures used in local authorities and build e-services upon already standardized procedures. The ideal is to use BPMN notation.
21. It is very important to have general plan of IT development, including guidelines and recommendations. However, some kind of local autonomy must be provided to adjust general guidelines to local situation.
22. Every bill has to have moneys attached to it – it should be clear what cost each bill generates and where are those money come from.
23. It is necessary to include the punishment clauses in each bill – formulating requirements with consequences leads to misconduct.
24. Budgetary system has to take into account the fact that the IT projects last longer than one year.
25. Provide public information campaigns on the benefits of on-line local public services.
26. Editing and distributing tutorials on how to access and obtain e-services.
27. Diversify the channels of public information on the processes taking place in local authorities, including by electronic means.
28. Providing support and technical assistance, advisory to supply municipalities with equipment and modern computers.
29. Promote the concept of outsourcing (outsourcing of services) and attracting investments for modernization of the LPA.
30. Providing technical and specialized assistance in computer equipment maintenance for local governments.
31. Provide assistance and logistical and technical support for the development of databases and electronic data processing programs.
32. Provide technical and logistical assistance required to process data records from the archives accumulated in municipalities.
33. Strengthen knowledge, skills of local civil servants on the use of information technology and data security and information assurance, possibly within centers of excellence in e-governance and e-public services.

⁵ For instance in Poland’s governmental Electronic Document Management.

34. Implementation of pilot projects in local authority for testing mechanisms in providing on-line services.
35. Promoting the creation of attractive conditions within municipalities for attracting and hiring young specialists.
36. Operation of changes in the legal framework that would allow the reduction of the number of certificates issued for local public services.
37. Systemic approach, coordinated nationally, based on the principles of subsidiarity of the problems of implementation of e-services in local government.
38. Conducting scientific research, studies on the premises and societal impact of electronic public services, particularly in local government, that are the main providers of services; for prioritization and objectives, identifying the best solutions and joint efforts of all social actors in the implementation of e-Government.
39. Develop a suitable methodological framework to the new realities on the implementation and provision of e-services in local governments.
40. Encouraging the private sector and civil society to participate in developing and implementing advanced solutions for telecommunications, based on the latest achievements in information technology and communications, public management, in other relevant areas: e-commerce, e-medicine e-education etc.
41. Implementation in LPA of the pilot projects in public management solutions locally and dissemination of best practices at the national level.
42. Implementation of necessary technical standards, as important component for e-services.
43. Planning money for ICT in local budgets.
44. The bottom-up approach in implementation of local services - to take into consideration the local servants initiatives and wishes.

2.4. Online visibility & Public awareness

A special attention was given to the online visibility and PR activities during the project implementation in 2015.

Based on Google Analytics data from 2015, the project web page www.discus.idsi.md was visited by over 4,600 unique visitors from 97 countries, carrying more than 7,000 sessions.

All organised events were broadcast online on project web page www.discus.idsi.md and www.idsi.md with more than 1000 visualizations.

From the start of the project, was created the project Facebook page for a larger dissemination of project events and results. Therefore, posts on DISCUS and ISDI Facebook pages had more than 1700 visits on each page (were considered the posts with the maximum visits by users).

During project implementation period were elaborated and disseminated 7 Newsletters and 7 Factsheets, 3 versions of project brochures (1st issued in January, 2015 about project planned activities, goal; 2nd issued in October – to present the results of the project during 10 months; 3rd was issued in November – December (in 2 versions) as a final project brochure). The brochures were distributed to all participants during project events and other external events. Brochures and factsheets were used during TV and Radio shows. All project materials were published on the project web page: www.discus.idsi.md (in Romanian and English) and periodically were sent by email to DISCUS events participants.

Due to the high level of interest shown by DISCUS events participants , during October-December 2015 were elaborated, printed and distributed several types of PR materials with project & IVF logos: 8GB memory sticks (containing all project materials, research studies); 3 types of bags; pens; T-shirts; small flags.

Also, there were published (or taken over from the project web page and re-published) many materials, articles on different national and foreign on-line portals and web pages (besides the project web page and ISDI, project partners' official pages), as follows:

Wep page/ portal	Short description/ relevance
www.unimedia.info	the most popular national news portal in Moldova. Were published 3 articles about project events and results, totally registered 4298 visits (at 04.01.16)
www.realitatea.md	National portal with 2 500 000 views, 350 000 unique visitors. 1 report (rerun 5 times) about DISCUS event was published and one TV show “Realitatea Azi” focused on DISCUS project.
www.logos.press.md	2 articles in Russian were published during December 2015 on logos press. The aim was to disseminate and to communicate about DISCUS project results to the Russian speaking population
www.centruinfo.org	announcements (in Romanian and English) about project events on Informational Centre for Local Authorities, Moldova web page and Facebook page
www.asm.md	4 news/ announcements about project events on the Academy of Sciences of Moldova web page
www.calm.md	announcement about DISCUS event on Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova web page
www.casata.md	announcement about project event on the local portal for LPAs
www.agenda.md	announcement about DISCUS event on the national portal where are published news about important events (mainly at the central level, of national interest)
www.ieg.asm.md	announcement about project event on Institute of Ecology and Geography of ASM web page
www.il.md	news about project event on Ialoveni District Council web page
www.plazamp3.net	online streaming of the first project event on the portal for online streaming
www.singerei.md	3 articles about 2 project events and study visit in Slovakia on Singerei District Council web page
www.costesti.md	article about project event on Costesti LPA web page
www.cancelaria.gov.md	article about project event from November on State Chancellery web page
www.zielonka.pl	news about DISCUS study visit of Moldovan group at the city hall of Zielonka, Poland
www.piotrkow.pl	news about DISCUS study visit of Moldovan group at the city

	hall of Piotrkow city, Poland
www.biblioteka.piotrkow.pl	news about DISCUS study visit of Moldovan group, at the library from Piotrkow city, Poland

PR activities

More than **5 hours of TV and 5 hours at Radio** of several shows, interviews, and reportages were broadcast about DISCUS project events, results, materials and impact.

For a larger dissemination were chosen **3 TV channels** as follows:

Moldova 1 TV (National Public Company): 2 appearances at TV shows “Cine vine la noi” (Who comes to us); 2 appearances and 5 reportages at “Bună dimineața” (Good Morning).

Realitatea TV (Reality TV, national): 5 reportages, 1 Talk show “Realitatea Azi” (Reality Today).

Mirador TV company: 105 minutes of several reportages (large interviews with project Visegrad and national experts; participants at project events).

The audience of Realitatea TV is: 18 – 65 age national audience. The materials about DISCUS posted on Realitatea TV had on 16.12.2015 – 2889 viewers (average minute ratings).

Nr	TV channel, show	Date, time	Link
1	<u>Moldova 1 TV</u> Morning Show “Buna dimineata”	Dec 1, 2015 Dec 2, 2015 Dec 4, 2015 Dec 8, 2015 Dec 10, 2015	http://www.trm.md/ro/buna-dimineea-a/buna-dimineata-din-1-decembrie-2015-partea-i/ http://www.trm.md/ro/buna-dimineea-a/buna-dimineata-din-2-decembrie-2015-partea-i/ http://www.trm.md/ro/buna-dimineea-a/buna-dimineata-din-4-decembrie-2015-partea-i/ http://www.trm.md/ro/buna-dimineea-a/buna-dimineata-din-8-decembrie-2015-partea-i/ http://www.trm.md/ro/buna-dimineea-a/buna-dimineata-din-10-decembrie-2015-partea-i/
2	<u>Moldova 1 TV</u> Morning Show “Buna dimineata”	Nov 27, 2015 Nov 17, 2015	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X3-4BnMEfg&feature=em-upload_owner#action=share http://www.trm.md/ro/buna-dimineea-a/buna-dimineata-din-17-noiembrie-2015-partea-i/
3	<u>Moldova 1 TV</u> Show “Cine vine la noi”	Oct 20, 2015 Oct 21-22, 2015	http://www.trm.md/ro/cine-vine-la-noi/cine-vine-la-noi-emisiune-din-20-octombrie-2015-partea-i/
4	<u>Realitatea TV</u> reportages	Dec 9, Dec 10, 2015 at: 18:00, 19:00, 21:00 07:30, 08:30	http://www.realitatea.md/revistele-stiintifice-----catalizator-al-cresterii-calitatii-si-vizibilitatii-continutului-stiintific-in-format-digital--video-31561.html
5	<u>Realitatea TV,</u> TV show “Realitatea Azi”	Dec 14, 2015 (duration 46:40)	http://www.realitatea.md/emisiuni/realitatea-azi.html/72663

DISCUS experts and ISDI representatives participated at **Radio shows**:

Radio Moldova (National Public Company)

Programs: 2 appearances at “Spațiul Public” (Public Space), 2 appearances at “Matinal Național” (National Matinal), 1 show “Loc de Dialog” (Place of dialogue).

Univers FM: full Radio show “Pachet Social” (Social Package)

Vocea Basarabiei (Voice of Bessarabia): 5 full Radio shows “Vocea APL” (Voice of LPA).

Nr	Radio channel	Date, time	Link
1	Radio Moldova, program “Spatiu public”	Nov 30, 2015 (duration 15 min) Dec 11, 2015 (duration 17 min)	http://idsi.md/files/file/publicatii/2015/30_11-SOCIETATEA_INFORMATIONALA.mp3 http://idsi.md/files/file/publicatii/2015/11_12_15-Spatiu_Public-despre-masa-rotunda-Continut-Digital.MP3
2	Radio Moldova, program “Matinal national”	Oct 20, 2015	http://www.trm.md/ro/matinal-national/matinal-national-din-20-octombrie-2015-partea-i-a/
3	Radio Moldova, program “Loc de dialog”	Nov 25, 2015 (duration 45 min)	http://idsi.md/files/file/publicatii/2015/25%2011%20%20LOC%20DE%20DIALOG%20SOCIETATEA%20INFORMATIONALA.mp3
4	Univers FM, radio show “Pachet social”	Oct 21, 2015	
5	Radio Vocea Basarabiei, program “Vocea APL”	Dec 12, 2015	http://www.calm.md/libview.php?l=ro&idc=59&id=2579&t=/SERVICIUL-PRESA/Emisiuni-Audio/Vocea-Administratiei-Publice-Locale-din-12-decembrie-2015

Overall were broadcast:

7 full Radio shows, 5 radio reportages

1 full TV show, more than 20 TV reportages and 10 interventions/interviews during TV shows (of approx. 15 min. each).

During project implementation period were published 5 articles in 4 national newspapers and journals: **Akademios** (Romanian), **Logos Press** (Russian), **Făclia** (Romanian), **Moldova Suverană** (Sovereign Moldova) (Romanian).

In addition, the message of the DISCUS project, as well as its results were disseminated through promoting on **Displays in Trolleys** (public transport in Chisinau, the capital of Moldova) during **2 months**; as a short video spot about DISCUS project.

Besides PR activities mentioned above, during the project implementation period the project objectives, project activities, research studies and study visits results were presented and disseminated within several national and international events, such as: *Moldova ICT Summit 2015*, April, Chisinau; Conference – *Decentralization: the path to modernization of the Republic of Moldova*, December 2015, Chisinau; during several events held at Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Academy of Public Administration, e-Government Center and other relevant institutions/public authorities.

2.5. General project results and impact

During project implementation, aiming to achieve the project goal and for more efficient project activities, ISDI established a large dialogue with the most important stakeholders in the information society field (including e-services and digital content):

- **Diplomatic corps:** Slovak Embassy in Chisinau;
- **Central bodies** (Ministries & State agencies): Ministry of ICT; Ministry of Culture; State Chancellery; State Agency for Intellectual Property of the Republic of Moldova; SE MoldData; National Center for Personal Data Protection, e-Government Center;
- **Academia sector** (R&D institutions, libraries, universities): Cultural Heritage Institute of the Academy of Sciences; National Library of Moldova; State University of Moldova; Engineering Sciences and Technology Section of ASM; Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences of ASM and other research institutions of ASM; editorial boards of Moldovan scientific journals;
- **Development programs** (local & foreign), **NGOs:** Quito Romania; Joint Integrated Local Development Programme, UNDP Moldova; Open Government Institute; Public Policy Institute; USAID Local Government Support Project in Moldova; Novateca program; Library Association from Moldavia; Small Business Association of Moldova;
- **Local Public Authorities:** 33 districts (rayons) including villages and cities; Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova;
- **Media sector:** 3 TV channels; 3 Radio channels; newspapers/ journals; news portals (local, national and foreign).

Involving different stakeholders within project activities, enabled the DISCUS Platform to become a focal point, an efficient communication platform for all stakeholders interested in information society development process in Moldova.

Totally, during 2015 the DISCUS project delivered:

- 6 events** in Chisinau: 2 workshops & 2 seminars – focused on LPA and local e-services; 2 roundtables focused on digital content;
- 2 study visits** in Poland and Slovakia;
- 5 research studies** in English and Romanian;
- 70 presentations** by **40 speakers** - national professionals and **3 experts** from the Visegrad countries;

More than **430 participants** (mayors, deputy mayors, secretaries of local councils, specialists from LPA and CPA, public servants, representatives of academic sector and of civil society) from 33 districts (rayons) of the Republic of Moldova.

Table 3.1. Project expected/attained results

Nr	Project expected results	Project attained results
1.	Improved collaborative environment, due to established discussion platform on Information Society development issues, bringing together representatives of	a) The platform www.discus.idsi.md is offering the instruments for collaborative work b) IDSI is proposed to be a focal

	academic sector, business, civil society, mass-media and V4 experts;	point for LPA on ICT and e-services issues c) The 6 (4 planned + 2 additional) project events organized, created a community- the collaborative network for discussion of LPA common problems
2.	Increased participation of local authorities representatives in the decision making process;	The identified problems of LPAs in using ICT tools for local services development, transformed into formulated recommendations for Central Public Authorities to be taken into consideration in legal/regulatory/ policy documents.
3.	Improved policy documents, based on the analysed and discussed best practices	V4 experts shared and discussed experience and best practices, and have written down in 4 printed Research Studies and Final Report posted on Discus website a set of guidance documents, for any local public servant, as well as IDSI consultancy
4.	Liaison between local authorities representatives and relevant V4 partners as result of study visits	The contacts established during the study visits between local authorities representative creates new opportunities for further collaborative work.

Local Public Authorities representatives benefited through enhancing their institutional capacity for participation in the decision-making process on central level, study visits that contributed to exchange of best practices, as well as strengthening collaboration with V4 countries and will continue to benefit using the created platform with all posted information. The draft action plan for implementation of local e-services will boost the ICT-driven local development. Policy making authorities are already benefitting from extended networking with representatives of academic sector, business, civil society, mass-media and V4 experts on Information Society development issues, reinforcing the effective application of information society policies and getting valuable feedback by means of Recommendations on new/amended public policies, regulations based on V4 best practices. The IDSI aims to become a country-level focal point for consulting local governments on ICT based services.

Because Moldova has embarked upon implementation of the strategic goals aligned with Digital Agenda for Europe through national strategies on building information society, through the project, national policy makers have an instrument for permanent support for consulting and improving draft policy, legal and regulatory documents before launching them

through the official decision making process within Government institutions, based on best practices of V4 countries. Recommendations on public policies' amendments based on V4 best practices and the input of seminars' participants will contribute towards enhanced policy/legal/regulatory documents. Development of the draft action plan for implementation of local e-services in rural localities will lead to improved citizen services. A general template of the action plan for e-services implementation was provided within the project to all participants at DISCUS events.

The project was assessed positively by the government representatives (State Chancellery) and Academy of Sciences of Moldova management during project events, especially during the workshop from November 24-25, 2015 (the biggest project event, attended by 120 people).

During the events, the local representatives had the opportunity to express their problems and visions on how they can solve their problems with ICTs. National and Visegrad experts consulted and advised representatives of LPAs. Visegrad experts presented some of their national best practices, as models to inspire the Moldovan public servants, both at the central and local levels.

It should be mentioned that Visegrad experts shared with Moldovan participants not only good practices of Visegrad countries, but also the lessons learnt, so that Moldova has an advantage now –avoiding the same mistakes. Direct discussions between different participants, experts, professionals facilitated communication and networking, including establishing new contacts and planning new ideas for future projects (local, national, regional). Local servants had a good opportunity to find out about their colleagues and their results in the field of e-services.

The study visits in Poland and Slovakia have influenced positively 7 local servants and 2 researchers. The participants could witness a lot of good examples – concrete e-services provided by local authorities in Visegrad/European countries. They have been inspired and returning home, they proposed to implement some relevant good examples from Poland and Slovakia. An important feature of the DISCUS project is that more than 430 people from Moldova became aware of what e-services mean and how they can influence the public administrative processes, as well as decision-making process.

DISCUS has become a unique communication platform in Moldova, where central authorities can meet face to face with local representatives, civil society members and other relevant stakeholders.

According to the evaluation questionnaires, the participant's expectations were met and they appreciated the opportunity to express their opinions concerning local problems and to propose plans on how these can be solved with ICT tools. It means that LPAs need periodical dialogue with different stakeholders: government representatives, academia sector, civil society etc. In this respect, during 2015 DISCUS became an efficient Discussion on Information Society Development Issues Platform. Starting from events of 50 – 60 participants (in March 2015) DISCUS platform managed to gather more than 120 representatives of different sectors: government, LPAs, academia, civil society, media in November 2015.

During the DISCUS events, the participants from 33 districts from the Republic of Moldova mentioned that DISCUS should be a permanent platform of communication, where all interested parties could meet regularly and discuss problems vs (IT) solutions for public

services (with an accent on the local level). DISCUS has become a common “place” where all development partners/stakeholders can put on agenda their ideas, proposals and plans.

3. Republic of Moldova: Country context 2015 (desk research)

3.1. Political and economic context

The Republic of Moldova, a landlocked country with borders to Romania and Ukraine, has a resident population of 3.5 million with a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita of EUR 1,687 in 2014. At the start of 2015, 58.6% of men and 56.7% of women were living in rural areas. Per capita disposable incomes in rural areas were 28.7% lower than in urban areas in 2014.

In early 2015, Moldova was an incumbent government, led by Liberal Democrat Iurie Leanca. Liberal Democrats, the Democrats and the Liberals negotiated at that time create a majority coalition after parliamentary elections in November 2014. Following November 2014 parliamentary elections, a new minority government was formed in February 2015, after intense negotiations. The appointment of a new government, composed of PLDM (Liberal-Democratic Party) and PDM (Democratic Party), has restored fragile stability after a prolonged period of political uncertainty. The three parties have reached a consensus and, on February 18, 2015, the minority Government led by Cyril Gaburici was nominated with the Democrats, Communists and Liberal Democrats' votes.

Local elections took place in 2015 and an election of a new President by Parliament will take place in 2016. The elections of November 2014 have shown there is a deep polarization in society. The PSRM (Socialist Party) has emerged as the largest party, obtaining a quarter of seats in Parliament.

In nearly four months in office, Cyril Gaburici has resigned and negotiations for a new coalition started, this time by hiring liberals.

On July 30 the new Liberal Democrat government led by Valeriu Strelet was invested and then dismissed on October 29 after less than three months in the office.

The negotiations between political parties until the middle of December 2015 did not achieve yet the consensus in nomination of the new Prime Minister.

The deep political and economic crisis during 2015 that Moldova is experiencing causes instability and mistrust of the population in the authorities (only 6 % of population trust in the Government).⁶

Thousands of protesters have camped out in central Chisinau since early September demanding resignations of senior government officials and early elections.

Moldova's economy faced a difficult situation in 2014 linked to several factors, including uncertainty related to the situation in Ukraine. Economic growth rates reduced from 8.9% in 2013 to 4.6% in 2014. Some projections foresee that the economic growth of Moldova could be negative in 2015.

Serious problems in Moldova's financial sector pose a risk to stable economic development. Stability in the banking sector, and as a result in the economy as a whole, has been severely undermined by a major banking fraud scandal in which possibly up to EUR 1 billion has been siphoned off fraudulently from three systemic banks (Banca de Economii, Banca Sociala, Unibanka), currently put under special administration by the NBM (National Bank of Moldova) and now in the process of liquidation. About 80% of the total commercial

⁶ Public Opinion Barometer- Nov. 2015 - www.ipp.md

sector banking assets are either under special administration or under special supervision (Victoriabank, Moldinconbank, Moldova-Agroindbank) by the National Bank of Moldova. The non-banking financial sector, especially the insurance sector, is also facing structural problems as a result of weak oversight and poor corporate governance.

The macro-fiscal situation is a source of increasing concern with revenues lagging behind, and the budget deficit increasing and there is a risk of delay in payment of salaries for public servants and pensions for retired people.

These political and economic problems have influenced the discussions on the DISCUS platform. During summer 2015 were organized local national elections, several new young people became mayors or deputy of villages and cities in Moldova. A lot of them participated immediately (after elections, IInd round) in September at DISCUS seminar, held in Chisinau. A big interest was shown by the newly elected servants for information society development at the local level in Moldova.

3.2. Public Administration reforms context

The Republic of Moldova territorial administration is highly fragmented with 32 districts (rayon), 66 cities (towns), of which five with municipality status, and with 898 local communities, the autonomous territorial unit of Gagauzia and territorial unit Stinga Nistrului (Transdnistria). Gagauzia is a region with the predominantly Christian-Orthodox population speaking a Turkish dialect. It is governed by Moldovan laws, as well as normative acts issued by the Gagauzian Parliament. Gagauzia has the right to independently determine issues relating to its political, economic and cultural development. Although Transdnistria is formally and internationally considered to be a part of Moldova, the Moldovan authorities do not exercise any control over this breakaway region.

According to the Decentralization Strategy, there are 3 development regions: North, Centre and South Development Regions. They don't have any formally given public administrative powers and are oriented to implementation of development projects, which cover more than 1 raion.

Each raion (district) elects a council which co-ordinates the activities of the local councils, in order to provide public services on district or municipal level. The councils are elected on the basis of universal, equal and direct suffrage by secret ballot for a term of four years.

The relations between the central and local public administration can be called supervision. The State Chancellery is responsible for the organization of the administrative control of the legality of the activity of the local public administration authorities, exercised by its own agencies or via subordinated territorial offices.

There is a doubtful status of the services in second-level LPAs' responsibility and the confusion between those and the deconcentrated services. The administrative legislation and practice of the Republic of Moldova does not establish clearly, which are the fundamental differences between the decentralized services, the deconcentrated and delegated ones. There is a tendency amongst several CPA's institutions to consider, in practice, the district decentralized services/institutions as being deconcentrated services/institutions, in respect of which they can influence and exercise directly and voluntarily their managing authority.

Moreover, different reports analysing the general condition in the public sector of the Republic of Moldova underline the exaggerated growth of such, especially regarding the public expenditures in the Gross National Product (further – GNP) in comparison with the level of development measured by the GNP/resident index, and suggest the restriction of its expansion. This factor has a special influence on the decentralization process, because of the extreme restriction of the fiscal space necessary for a better financing of the LPA. Public Administration Reform (PAR) is a cross-cutting issue and a pre-condition for adequate implementation of the reforms according to the seven priority sectors within the National Development Strategy Moldova 2020. As PAR may not be a singled out priority, however it is widely acknowledged that the civil service and more generally public administration are in urgent need of restructuring, enhanced capacity, greater efficiency and transparency.

The EU-Moldova Association Agreement signed on 27 June 2014 calls upon the Government of Moldova to deepen the cooperation in relation to the Public Administration Reform focusing on: the development of efficient, transparent, inclusive and accountable public administration. These elements are in line with the Principles on Public Administration published by SIGMA (Support for Improvement in Governance and Management) in November 2014⁷.

There is an evident lack of financial and administrative autonomy for regional authorities in Moldova, which are limited in decision-making powers regarding their own administrative structure and bound some very heavy delegated responsibilities and are thus more dependent than ever before on the central authorities. Distribution of responsibilities between two different levels of public power is, in fact, a system of diffusion of power, rather than proper decentralization.⁸

The strategic framework for Public Administration Reform (PAR) is not complete notwithstanding a draft PAR strategy was prepared in 2013 with the support of the World Bank. A number of subsector strategies are adopted but there is no clear synergy between them. An overarching Public Administration Reform Strategy and its accompanying Action Plan is overdue and is considered critical in order to pursue further reform.

There PAR policy development system has weaknesses due to lack of skills and of effective policy coordination, limited focus on strategic planning and limited evidence-based policy due to unavailability of timely and quality statistical data. Regulatory process is hampered by lack of coordination between the bodies involved in the policy coordination: Ministry of Foreign Affairs for the monitoring of implementation of the Association Agreement, State Chancellery as body in charge of the policy coordination of the Government, relevant line ministries and agencies and Parliament of Moldova.

Fiscal decentralisation was rolled-out to country-wide as of 1 January 2015. The lack of reform of the number of territorial units did not contribute to strengthen the already weak capabilities of the majority of local authorities.

⁷ The principles of public administration, SIGMA, November 2014, <http://www.sigmaweb.org/publications/Principles-Public-Administration-Nov2014.pdf>

⁸AER Regionalism. Report by country – Moldova, 2010 http://www.aer.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/MainIssues/Regional_Democracy/AER_Regionalism_Report/Report_by_country/MOLDOVA_2010.pdf

As stated in the latest European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) Progress Report 2014⁹, Moldova made limited progress on depoliticising and professionalising its central public administration, in the absence of a clear strategy for public administration reform. The average salaries of civil servants remained low and the civil service remained structurally weak due to staff moving to the private sector or to international organisations.

Concerning human resources management, despite of new Human Resource Management system, the question of low salaries of civil servants remain as one of the main issues of concern. Motivation and training are two fields where it is possible to incentive the permanence in the Public Sector. The staff turnover is 11% on average for 2014 (16% only in the Central Public Administration).

The recent (December 17-18, 2015) Conference "Decentralization: the path towards modernization of Moldova" found the lack of progress towards decentralization and continue preserving the current political-administrative system highly centralized, politicized clientele, outdated and ineffective, dominated by certain narrow groups of interests outside of the real control by society.¹⁰

Discussions within DISCUS platform touched some of the topics related to public administration reform and limited rights of local government, that hamper their possibilities to develop ICT-based local services.

3.3. Information Society Development context

DISCUS project as an Information Society Development issues platform was focused on main development problems of ICT-based local services. However, to develop ICT-based services, the proper environment should be in place.

According to the latest data, Moldova has some good positions in international rankings on the development of the information society. Some of this good positioning of our country in studies and reports includes:

- ICT Development Index (61st place out of 166)¹¹;
- e-Government Development Index of the United Nations (66th place out of 193)¹²;
- e-Participation Index of the United Nations (40th place out of 193);
- Network Readiness Index (68th out of 143)¹³;
- Global Cybersecurity Index (16th place out of 29)¹⁴.
- Competition in Internet and telephony (position 1 from 143 countries)
- The adult literacy rate (position 14 with the index of 99.40 percent)

⁹ Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2014 http://eeas.europa.eu/enp/pdf/2015/enp-regional-report-eastern_partnership_en.pdf

¹⁰ <http://calm.md/libview.php?l=ro&idc=66&id=2592>

¹¹ Measuring the Information Society Report 2014 / Geneva: International Telecommunication Union, 2014. 250 p.

¹² United Nations E-Government Survey 2014. E-Government for the Future We Want, UN, New York 2014 https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/Portals/egovkb/Documents/un/2014-Survey/E-Gov_Complete_Survey-2014.pdf

¹³ The Global Information Technology Report 2015: ICTs for Inclusive Growth / Ed.by S. Dutta et al. Geneva: World Economic Forum, INSEAD, 2015. 357 p.

¹⁴ Global Cybersecurity Index & Cyberwellness Profiles. April 2015 / International Telecommunication Union Geneva: ITU, 2015. 515 p.

- Internet Broadband International traffic (position 24 with a rate of 115.80 kb / s per user) e-participation index (position 40, and a rate of 0.63 of 1)
- Fixed broadband Internet availability (position 44 and a price of \$ 26.51 PPP / month)
- Broadband internet subscribers (mobile: 47th with 47.20 to 100 inhabitants, fixed: position 52 and an index of 13.40 to 100 inhabitants)
- The share of highly qualified jobs (position 48 and a percentage of 30 percent)
- Internet access in schools (position 49 and the index value of 4.90)
- Online government services index (position 60 and the index value of 0.53).

However, a number of indicators on information society development in Moldova remain to be located at low levels, both in European and the international media. These include:

- Judicial independence index value of 2.00 (position 140 of 143 countries)
- Efficiency of the judiciary in the changing regulatory environment (position 133, index 2.30)
- Innovation capacity (position 127, index 2.30)
- The efficiency of the judicial system in resolving disputes (position 127, index 3.00)
- Government purchases of high technology (position 126, index 2.70)
- Quality of management schools (heading 125, index 3.20)
- The level of staff training (position 119, index 3.40)
- Protection of intellectual property (position 117, index 2.80)
- Availability of equity (position 116, index 2.20)

In the Republic of Moldova the main necessary legislative and normative framework was created for building information society. It currently includes more than 20 laws, 80 Government decisions, about 70 approved conceptual documents regarding the information systems of public authorities, more than 20 general purpose regulatory acts and 75 with a specific purpose issued by ANRCETI. The relevant institutional framework is in place which includes the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications, The National Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Information Technology (ANRCETI), National Radio Frequency Center, Center for Electronic Governance and National Center for Personal Data Protection.

Strategic Program for Governance Technological Modernization (e-Transformation), supported by the World Bank, was adopted in 2011. In 2013 the National Strategy “Digital Moldova 2020” was approved by the Government and is being implemented. Recently, the Government approved a package of initiatives to increase the competitiveness of the IT industry: the draft Strategy for the years 2015-2020 and the draft Law on information technology industry parks, aimed at creating the prerequisites for boosting development of the information technology industry oriented towards export.

Moldova ranks 3rd among CIS countries and 40th in the world, according to e-Participation Index (EPI). This is due to policies aimed at active development of e-government services and provision of necessary information on the websites of government agencies, as well as active use of tools aimed at involvement of citizens in government decision making.

In this regard, it is worth mentioning the Government's Open Data portal (<http://www.date.gov.md/>), which started in 2011 and expresses the government interest in developing transparent management and innovation to support the citizens. This portal is one of the most important elements of government e-transformation. It was institutionalized by a decree, according to which every state agency or ministry must publish its lists of open data. In 2015, the portal has published some 874 datasets and 4313 resources, while during 2014 more than 160 800 datasets were downloaded from the portal. The Information Society Development Institute (<http://www.idsi.md>) developed a unique database of research projects (<http://www.expert.asm.md>) and a unique database of national scientific publications (<http://www.ibn.idsi.md>).

In order to reduce the digital and technological divide between rural and urban areas, a series of projects and programs were launched in Moldova, among these the five-year program “Novateca”, implemented in partnership with the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, IREX, USAID and “Microsoft” corporation. This program is providing Moldovan citizens with access to relevant information and modern, locally tailored services in public libraries.

According to ITU experts ICT sector in Moldova is one of the main drivers of change in society and business and recorded an upward dynamic. Information Society is declared a national priority and how will this be done depends on the ability of authorities to determine the correct directions of development and to mobilize the necessary resources.

Experts consider also that for Moldova, which lacks natural deposits or own energy resources, the human capital and creating favorable conditions for harnessing its potential can provide an added economic value.

Studies (www.anrceti.md) show that over 80% of Internet users are surfing on it daily or almost daily, 75 percent of households Republic of Moldova have Internet fixed and mobile dedicated Internet connection. 80.5 % of home Internet users browsing it daily or almost daily.

With reference to the market of broadband Internet access (fixed and mobile Internet dedicated), market research shows that Internet visitors typically use this service to communicate through Skype, Viber etc. (82%) access social networks (81%), news pages (67%), weather forecast data (63%) of a professional search information and studies (61%) etc.

The conclusions drawn from such statistics are that mainly telecommunication services are used for consumption. Below the average of countries in the lower-middle-income group lies the indicator of Business usage. The indicator on the economic impact of ICT is also at a low rate. .

In those circumstances, a very topical issue in terms of ICT development in Moldova is, that in spite of the fact that the infrastructure is generally good, particularly in communications, there is qualified personnel in place, a sufficiently high level of adult literacy, an important share of jobs requiring knowledge-intensive economic, the impact of ICT is not at the expected level. The level of ICT use in business is low and the IT industry in Moldova is not efficient, its share in gross domestic product is below 1 percent. The ICT sector is over 90 percent based only on communications. All this, plus a high level of piracy will need to be the subject of interest for future ICT policy.

Data presented by the World Economic Forum indicates the ineffectiveness of policies and regulatory framework in ICT. Identifying solutions to improve them shall be a

key priority in the development of ICT. Given that ICT sector share in GDP is 8-10% (IT share is less than 1%), the strategy for improvement of IT industry competitiveness for 2015-2021 has recently been approved (2015)¹⁵.

These changes stand for a substantial transformation of IT state policy. Meanwhile, one of the weaknesses of the country, in the context of implementation of the WSIS Plan of Action is the lack of venture capital funds (2.2 out of 7), lack of multilateral ICT partnerships, despite the fact that Moldova has approved the Law on public-private partnership. It should also be noted, there is not a unique national program for information society development, therefore ministries and departments develop their own ICT strategic development programs.

3.4. Conclusions and recommendations on ICT development

Despite of the more or less favorable conditions for information society development set up in the country, these should be strengthened.

State policies should focus on developing a clear action plan for using ICT to improve the global competitiveness of the country. Given the fact, that there is a lack of venture capital funds, it is necessary to develop a series of measures to easier availability of venture capital funds and boost the use of multilateral partnerships for the development and implementation of Information Society policies. Another important factor is ensuring adequate financing for the implementation of approved strategies.

One of the major priorities in the infrastructure building area shall be increasing involvement of local ICT companies in developing government IT systems.

In the area of access to information and knowledge, practical steps are needed to provide public access points to information for the citizens, including information on the activities of state organizations on their official websites, taking into account providing access to people with disabilities.

In terms of capacity building, the training of qualified ICT staff should be set as a national priority. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a network of competence centers in areas outside the capital, to strengthen young people's digital potential. Measures aimed to increase the ICT competence of teachers is necessary, the development of motivation mechanisms to increase the use of interactive methods and modern ICTs in the teaching process.

In terms of building confidence and security in the use of ICT, special attention should be paid on training courses on information security.

It is necessary to increase the efficiency of ICT implementation at the regional level, because ICT tools are poorly implemented at the local level, due to the lack of funding and qualified staff. Government support is needed regarding the implementation of IT systems at the local level, as well as institutionalization of an IT consultancy center for the local authorities.

It is necessary to ensure widespread computerization of medical institutions in both urban and rural areas motivating medical staff to use ICTs, user trainings.

It is necessary to promote the active use of ICTs, as a tool for environmental protection and sustainable use of natural resources.

¹⁵ Hotărârea Guvernului Republicii Moldova nr. 254 din 05.14.2015 cu privire la aprobarea Strategiei de creștere a competitivității industriei tehnologiei informației pe anii 2015-2021

The country is an agrarian one and modern development requires ensuring the full integration of ICT in agriculture, rural development and systematic dissemination of information and knowledge in agriculture using ICTs.

It is recommended to elaborate a state program on e-Science development, to promote initiatives in the field of electronic publishing and open access and to support the development of ICT infrastructure for scientific research.

4. E-services context in the Republic of Moldova

In the Republic of Moldova, the e-Governance Center is the institution responsible on behalf of the Government for the implementation of the e-Transformation Agenda and set up a unique platform for public services provided by the central authorities - <https://servicii.gov.md/> portal. This platform functions as an electronic catalogue for public services provided by the authorities dedicated to citizens and the business. The main purpose of this platform is to offer brief, correct, accessible and complete information on the public services available in the Republic of Moldova.

On the platform, one can find information regarding both electronic services, as well as traditional services. The visitors can find the description of the services, the set of documents required for these services, the schedule of the services, the costs and the implementation duration. They can also find contact details for more information and the forms that have to be completed by the citizens in electronic format, including completion's guidance.

The platform is divided into service categories for:

- Citizens (information and petition, finance and taxes, licenses and special permits, etc.)
- Businesses (taxes, reports, confirming acts, permissive acts, etc.)
- Visitors (Moldovan citizenship, entry and stay in the Republic of Moldova)
- Life scenarios (emigration, immigration, business initiation, real estate, creating a family, health, studies)

Currently, there are 490 services on the portal, of which 112 are e-Services (on-line services) with data opened for access¹⁶. The Republic of Moldova Government is determined to transform all traditional counter services into e-services by 2020, through the „Open Government action plan” and the „Government technological modernization strategy”. This way, the citizens will be able to access over 500 e-services.

However, the speed of e-Transformation agenda implementation is not yet at the necessary level. Moreover, a substantial gap exists between the level of services offered at the central level and those offered at the local level. Therefore, the discussion platform offered by DISCUS project on ICT-driven local development, aimed to identify relevant issues and enhance local participation in the decision-making process could help in strengthening the capacities of local authorities on the one hand and in involvement of central public authorities, academic sector and civil society in discussion of LPA problems on the other hand.

According to *Public Services Reform Program approved by the Government*¹⁷, re-engineering of public services is one of the most urgent priorities of the Government of Moldova, but also a major challenge that requires rethinking and transforming traditional

¹⁶ National e-services portal <https://servicii.gov.md/> accessed on 23.12.2015

¹⁷ Hotărîrea Guvernului nr.122 din 18 februarie 2014

patterns of activity of public authorities and institutions. The vertically organized public institutions that operate within the strict limits of the powers set by normative acts are to be restructured into a single system, that will remove institutional barriers, will develop horizontal linkages and cooperation instruments that provide efficient organization of public services for citizens and entrepreneurs and economical use of resources of central and local public authorities. This is necessary due to the rapid development of technological innovations, as well as the increasing demands of society. The project on public services modernization, developed by the European Commission, states: "Today citizens know their rights better and better, have more information about public services and therefore have higher expectations and requirements to the quality of services"¹⁸

The Program identified two main groups of issues related to public service reform.

The first group aimed at service system itself, covering such issues as quality of service, accessibility of information on services, the time required to obtain a specific service, the possibility to choose the channels for offering service to beneficiaries, respecting rule of law in the provision of services, reasonable costs for citizens and businesses, service culture, ensuring service delivery infrastructure, organization of economically efficient services .

A second group of issues relates to public service reform itself and covers such issues as quality of reform policies by setting clear goals, principles and policy tools, activities and measures planned, correctness and their consistency with other government initiatives, primarily with e-transformation agenda, providing resources, establishing effective mechanisms for reform coordination and management, awareness by civil servants both at management level, and at the level of experts on essence and complexity of reform.

Generalization of the existing problems from the beneficiaries' perspective includes:

1) Incomplete information posted on the public institutions websites. In most cases to benefit from the necessary service, recipients are forced to visit in person the servicing institutions.

According to survey results, in 2013 - more than 50% beneficiaries have recognized that the information on the website about the required service was insufficient.

2) Narrow institutional approach and isolation of public institutions in organizing services. The beneficiary continues to act as a courier, ensuring the exchange of documents between public institutions. Although the interoperability of public registers is being implemented, it works only in isolated cases, requiring significant time and additional economic costs to citizens and businesses.

According to 2013 survey results - to get a distinct service, more than 30% of beneficiaries had to visit more than 3 institutions.

3) Lack of systematic procedures and practices to assess the administrative burden. The regulatory framework, which sets out the procedure for obtaining service, provides requirements that might yield without additional risks, but systematic assessment and identification of excessive existing procedures and processes are carried out only in separate cases, particularly in international technical assistance projects.

4) ***Arbitrary inclusion of additional requirements beyond of normative acts provisions (laws, government decisions, decisions by local authorities) established by the***

¹⁸ A vision for public services <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/vision-public-services>

institutions' internal instructions on the service. This requires the need for repeated visits to institutions to submit documents not covered by legal acts and not included in the lists of documents posted on institutions' websites. This way the time needed to get a service is increasing.

5) Lack of uniform and transparent principles for establishing tariffs for paid services. Prices for services are perceived by most people as arbitrary or unreasonable.

According to the survey results in 2013 - more than 58% of beneficiaries considered the tariffs for services as unjustified.

6) The existence of unofficial supplementary payments claimed by beneficiaries. The 2011 Survey, conducted by the International Republican Institute (IRI), Baltic Surveys / The Gallup Organization, showed that additional informal payments constituted the usual way of solving the problems of citizens interacting with public institutions in more than 80% of cases. According to the 2013 Survey, 47% of respondents admitted that unofficial payments were requested in the delivery of a service.

The general objective of the Public Service Reform Programme is to focus on ensuring the interests of society and service users.

As result indicators for the general objective, the following performance indicators (PIs) from the beneficiary's perspective:

PI 1: Reduce the time required to obtain information about services and service outcome.

PI 2: Reduce the number of visits to institutions to receive services.

PI 3: Reduce the distance to the provision of services.

PI 4: Reduce the cost of services for beneficiaries.

PI 5: Improve quality of service (satisfaction of beneficiaries).

PI 6: Reduce the number of complaints.

Specific objective 1. Ensure a coordinated and unified approach to improving public services and the implementation of the strategic program of technological modernization of governance (e-Transformation).

Outcome 1: normative and methodological framework for reforming public services, ensuring efficient management and coordination of reform.

PI 7: Preparation and approval of the law on public services.

Target for 2015: Draft law on public services developed, consulted with public institutions, central and local public authorities and non-governmental organizations, approved by the Government and presented to the Parliament.

PI 8: Draft Government decisions and methodologies on the implementation of civil service reform developed

Target for 2015: The set of laws and methodologies developed, consulted and duly approved.

Specific objective 2. Reengineering and modernization of public services through digitization.

Outcome 2: Increasing efficiency and effectiveness in terms of cost for public services, including those provided on-line (e).

PI 9: The number of active Web pages, application models, documents necessary to receive service available on-line, technical facilities that allow online applications integrated into the portal of public services www.servicii.gov.md.

Target for 2015: active web pages for all public services and forms that can be downloaded on-line - 30%.

PI 10: The share of public services subject of reengineering in accordance with the Methodology

2014: 10%; 2015: 30%; 2016: 50%.

PI 11: Share of approved administrative regulations for public services after their reengineering

2014: 10%; 2015: 30%; 2016: 50%.

As can be seen, the Program objectives are oriented to on-line services, including those offered by local public administrations.

The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016, approved by Government Decision on 25 June 2014 is one of the most important documents in approximation of the legal framework on Information Society and ICT based services, to those of EU. The progress in implementation of this plan could substantially help in implementation of ICT based services at local level.

The most recent published policy document relevant to ICT based public services development is the Government of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018¹⁹. The document inter alia provides for actions in adjustment of the normative-legal base for implementing government Interoperability Framework and of recommendations on interconnection and interoperability, as well as for implementation of access to registers and databases of national importance for all central and *local public authorities and institutions*, in accordance with the duties and functions of these authorities.

Practical steps have been undertaken in finding most relevant solutions for implementation of ICT based services at local level including with the support of development partners. The *UNDP Joint Integrated Local Development Programme (JILD)* which promoted and implemented locally e-government system by research and implementation of e-services in 30 JILD target communities²⁰ and USAID Local Government Support Project (LGSP) that developed the *Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center (CISC)*²¹.

The Concept was developed under a pilot project for modernizing the activity of local public authorities in the Republic of Moldova, based on the example of one LPA. Depending on the results obtained in the respective pilot project implementation, this Concept can be easily replicated in other local public administration authorities.

¹⁹ Program activity of the Govern of Moldova 2015-2018

<http://www.parlament.md/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=uskJCCIZKzg%3D&tabid=128&mid=506&language=ro-RO>

²⁰ Joint Integrated Local Development Programme

http://www.md.undp.org/content/moldova/en/home/operations/projects/poverty_reduction/joint-integrated-local-development-programme.html

²¹ Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center

http://descentralizare.gov.md/public/files/CIPS_Concept_paper_final_eng.pdf

Before bringing all services under the roof of CISC, the processes for providing the latter must be improved through remodeling, if needed. The remodeling process involves organization of workshops with the participation of representatives from the DS, ministries, and other actors involved in the service provision, identification of proposals for improving the current processes, using ICT solutions, as well as closer collaboration between DSs, LPAs, and other stakeholders involved in the service provision process. Some remodeling solutions require legislative amendments to be promoted, which may last a longer timeframe. Other operational solutions can be implemented in the short/immediate run, such as:

- Preparation of service provision related information and its posting on the LPA webpage, billboard, and publication in local mass media;

- LPA connection to the databases of State Enterprise Cadaster, State Enterprise CRIS Register, etc.;

- In the incipient phase – including in the documents' circulation the scanned electronic versions of documents and organizing the work mainly in electronic form in order for the original documents to reach the file only by the end of the procedures.

- Receiving requests for documents and intermediary services in a single point, at CISC, and consecutively engaging the CISC to contact the de-concentrated authorities to respond to the requests received on behalf of the applicants.

- Carrying out random visits and controls based on risk criteria with the intention to get mainly in-officio approvals (if the information provided allows this). Implementing a single point for payment for public services, as well as a system for providing all the information related costs and payments in the process of authorization.

The key duties of the CISC include improving the services provided by LPA and providing information to physical and legal entities. In this sense, CISC represents the main tool for accomplishing the objectives of the latter, the overall goal of which will be to provide good quality services in a prompt manner, upon submission of a minimum set of documents.

CISC, in its quality of LPA Front Office, will be used for providing all the existing public services currently provided by the LPA. Taking into account the fact that improving the efficiency of services is an on-going process, the services provided through CISC will be of different maturity level, as mentioned bellow, while the mayor's office staff will strive to develop the services and bring them to the highest level:

1. *Information* – Publication and dissemination of information. All the service provision related information will be published on the mayor's office webpage, and will be also made available through the guidelines issued and disseminated by CISC.

2. *Interaction* – The citizens will have the possibility to contact the mayor's office and deconcentrated services through the web page or upload template application forms and documents.

3. *Transaction* – The citizens will have the possibility to carry out full transactions in electronic form. For example, the possibility to file a request and related documents in electronic form without involving the applicant in the process of obtaining a permissive document. In the case of CISC, the service is considered to be a transaction when the applicants file a request at the CISC, while the whole circuit of document, access to information, and coordination with other authorities involved is ensured electronically and is transparent for the applicants.

4. *Transformation* – The public authorities transform the current operational process to provide more efficient, integrated, unified, and customized services. This level represents an integration of internal and external institutions and systems to insure full communication between the public authorities. In the case of CISC, a service is considered to be at the level of transformation when it is eliminated through exchange of information between the authorities.

CISC will fulfill its duties by accomplishing their goals, mission, and tasks in 2 (two) consecutive stages:

i) Preparation stage, which will involve creation of CISC, as a unit, approval of Internal Regulation, appointment of the Consultation Commission members, approval of the list of services provided by LPA, and of respective guidelines and regulations, as well as launching the CISC activity in an office designed for such purpose;

ii) Implementation stage, which will include procurement of software and hardware, required for CISC activity, staff training, piloting and starting full operation of CISC from organizational, operational and ICT points of view. In the 2nd stage, after the implementation of the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and of the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD), provided by Government through the e-Government Center (which will serve as a basis for the integrated information system of the mayor's office), the management and circulation of documents will take place in electronic form.

These systems will cover the entire circulation cycle of documents and information, starting with filing requests for obtaining services, for service provision, documents' circulation both within the mayor's office and de-concentrated services through communication and information exchange, and finishing with the archiving of documents.

Payment by clients will be made possible through the payment terminal installed in the premise of CISC, which will be connected to the ERLS.

However, the Concept of CISC could serve as a model for replication in local public authorities adjusting it to local needs.

5. Korea experience: INVIL-Smart village

INVIL project is considered one of the e-Government best practices from South Korea. Information Network Village (INVIL) Project is designed to reduce the digital divide between rural and urban regions by increasing availability of e-government services and to increase income level of local residents by boosting regional economy through e-commerce, which eventually leads to the improvement of the quality of life in rural communities.²²

With rapid informatization, the regional digital divide became one of the pressing social issues for Korea since around the end of the 1980s. In order to address this problem, the South Korean government launched the Information Network Village (INVIL) Project in 1990, which was designed to improve local residents' quality of living, boost the regional economy and manage an integrated e-government by narrowing the digital divide between urban and rural

²² About INVIL. Retrieved from <http://www.invil.org/english/intro1/about/>

areas. Critics often say that during the early years of the INVIL Project, the central government was too deeply involved in the project and implemented informatization education programs without considering the life style and educational level of rural residents, in particular elderly people. However, it is also true that for the last ten years, the INVIL Project helped villages form online communities, share the necessary information and boost the local economy through e-commerce transactions.²³

The Information Network Village (INVIL) aims at enabling rural communities to become self-sufficient through the provision of fast speed internet access. This reduces the digital divide between urban and rural areas. Through INVIL networks, rural communities are encouraged to exploit the possibilities of e-commerce for their products to foster sustainable growth in their regions. The INVIL networks incorporate participatory management systems and also contribute to the social integration of immigrants. Each community that takes part in INVIL is provided with ICT infrastructure, training and a Community Information Centre. ***Since 2001 to present 361 villages have been created and are operational.*** The main beneficiaries of the project are 500 000 inhabitants of rural areas have signed up for the INVIL project as of 2001.

INVIL Project implementation

Design (time: 5 months)

To achieve the goal of building ‘free-standing and self-sufficient communities,’ the central government initiated the INVIL project as a standard model for implementing ICT infrastructure in rural communities in 2001. Solidarity, residents’ willingness to take part in the program, and a detailed plan for improvement were the key criteria considered by the government when selecting target communities.

Testing (time: 1 month)

25 communities were taking part in an INVIL pilot project in 2001.

Implementation (time: 6 months)

Tools used:

- ICT technologies such as high speed network, INVIL portal, e-commerce, smart devices were used to establish information network village infrastructure.
- Information Network Village Steering Committee was established for encouraging autonomous management by the residents and a structured operation system was set up through Central Council where all the community members take part.

Resources used:

• *Network creation budget:*

- Initial stage of INVIL: KRW 0.3 billion for building high speed Internet networks, Community Information Centres, and the provision of PCs to rural citizens.
- Current stage: KRW 0.2 billion as PC ownership in rural areas has increased.

• *Operation budget:*

- Funds by the central government for education, consulting, central system and website maintenances: USD 33 million.

²³ http://idn.snu.ac.kr/?page_id=150

- Funds by local governments and communities for costs to run community information centres and manager's wages.
- Other costs for INVIL-related events such as 'Leader's festival for the INVIL' and a farmers' market called 'INVIL festa' that is held every year for public relations purposes.
- Additional resources provided by colleges contributing to the educational activities of INVIL.
- E-bay Korea supports INVIL with special offers for sales and promotion of INVIL products.

Diffusion (time: 12 years)

By 2013, a total of 361 INVIL villages were created through 13th phases.

The main partnerships developed within the INVIL project include:

Local governments / Other Public Sector

Local governments: screen business proposals from the communities and recommend candidates to the central government (including provincial finance); support the development of local digital contents; and provide training for village residents and administrative matters.

INVIL Central Council and Central operation agency / Private sector

- INVIL Central Council represented by community leaders: leads INVIL operation and management.
- Central operation agency: supports the operation for every village's management of the main website.

INVIL members (residents of villages) / Civil Society

INVIL members (residents of villages): compose the operation committee itself, develop their business model, operate the community information centre and website etc.

The government runs the main home page of the INVIL Project (www.invil.org), which links to the additional homepages of 361 participating villages. The website also provides various services with information on local products (www.invil.com), agritourism products (www.tour.invil.com), local news posted by local residents (www.news.invil.org) and online communities (www.community.invil.org).

INVIL Project results

The INVIL Project established various contents on its integrated homepage and enabled information network villages to share them and form communities. The homepage also provides the following services working with private and public sector organizations:

- E-Admin: civil affairs administration, including customer service and civil documents, and public contents like domestic acts and subordinate statutes, rules, procedure and public notice
- E-Biz: e-commerce services, promotional businesses, internet banking and economic and industrial content
- E-Edu: distance learning programs and education contents
- E-Healthcare: telemedicine services and health and medical related content
- E-Culture: Communities, internet reservations and cultural content

E-commerce sales significantly grew each year through ‘www.invil.com’ and ‘www.tour.invil.com,’ contributing to the income increase of rural residents. In fact, as agricultural and fishery products have certain problems in terms of production period, storage and transport, they are not perfect goods for online sale. Moreover, local residents have little understanding of e-commerce. Despite these problems, however, online sales are on the rise thank to education on e-commerce, service stabilization, and monthly and holiday promotion events.

The e-commerce sales of information network villages increased from 3 billion won in 2006 to around 4.5 billion won (up 50%) in 2007 and in the next year doubled to 9.1 billion won. The sales of agritourism products also showed a remarkable growth, up from 570 million won in 2006 to 1.4 billion won in 2007 and 2.8 billion won in 2008, becoming a new viable business model for information network villages.

The government has been supporting the villages to develop and improve various business models to make profits through e-commerce transactions and develop new specialties and agritourism products. This has been very helpful for the villages to strengthen their competitiveness and become self-reliant.

*Lessons learnt*²⁴

- While other public policies have centered on ‘giving people fish,’ the INVIL initiative was tailored by the approach of ‘teaching people how to fish.’ What we learned is that public policy designed to promote growth in marginalised regions involves huge amounts of investment to build facilities and other hardware resources. Yet, the approach of ‘giving people fish’ deprives them of the opportunity to learn how to fish and reduces their willingness, and even their awareness, of the need to fish.
- Through the INVIL initiative, the Ministry has also learned that continued investment and management based on a long-term vision is the key to its success. It requires much perseverance and investment over the long term to fundamentally change people’s awareness and establish a foundation for sustainable growth.
- Success also requires consistency in the role of the central government and excellent collaboration between the local governments and the communities.

The main conditions for success are public private partnership and sustainable growth.

South Korea’s Information Network Village Project is garnering high praise from the international community as a good practice of narrowing the digital divide and increasing the participation of residents in the digital world. The project is also appreciated as a successful case that increases tourism sales by promoting and marketing rural areas and improves rural household income by encouraging e-commerce transactions of local products. The INVIL Project received an award (World eGov Forum Trophy) at the World E-Government Forum held in France in 2006. The Project was showcased as a success case in several international events like the ‘Dynamic Korea Policy Forum’ in Beijing in 2007, the 2008 e-Challenge Exhibition in Sweden, the Local Government Managers Australia (LGMA) Meeting and the 2009 LMP General

²⁴https://www1.oecd.org/governance/observatory-public-sector-innovation/innovations/page/informationnetworkvillageinvilproject.htm#tab_lessons

Assembly in the Philippines. **The United Nation already designated the INVIL Project as one of the Millennium Development Programs, considering developing the project as an international cooperation program of the UN.**²⁵

Conclusions and recommendations

The experience of INVIL project could be implemented in Moldova, aiming to bring e-services and e-Government to residents of villages, which still represent the main part of the population. Tailoring INVIL to the national context, making use of the lessons learnt and the vast experience garnered during over 14 years of program implementation in Korea, could greatly benefit the Moldovan rural communities. Fostering the collaboration between the central government, local public authorities and the communities, INVIL project implementation in Moldova could lead to overcoming the urban-rural digital divide through ICT infrastructure and training of locals, establishing self-supporting rural communities through e-commerce and agritourism, all eventually leading to higher income and better quality of life in a sustainable way.

6. Lessons learnt from V4 countries experience

6.1. Czech Republic experience

On ICT-driven local development:

Successful creation and introduction of Information System of Public Administration (ISPA) at local level (region, district) is not possible without:

1. Creation of the legislative and normative uniform environment for all ISPA.
2. Creation of the Information system about data elements for:
 - working out not only of all ISPA,
 - creation of conditions for integrality of ISPA at all levels of PA.
3. Creation of a methodology for every ISPA, as base for software development.

All experiences to bypass the above-stated positions by working out ISPA at state level or ministerial level or local level have ended with a failure (Czech Republic 1994, Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs 1995, Ministry of Defence 1996 and the following). It concerns also some IS at state level, which are not ISPA (e.g. IS of vehicles 2014).

When these basic conditions are not respected and implemented, there are big losses of resources (big money, lost time, labour).

On e-services:

For working out IS for providing of e-services at local level it is necessary to have the data minimum from two IS of public administration - the Register of Inhabitants and IS of subject domain i.e. from which it is necessary to provide service.

Further, it is necessary to have means for the authorised conversion of documents, i.e. legal equivalence of documents in an electronic and paper form is provided.

²⁵ Innovation and Development Network, IDN (2012), "Information Network Village(INVIL) Project", Case Studies on Innovation and Development No. 2012-017

After solving these problems, it is possible to start working out of the project on providing of service in the form of e-service, maintenance of its documents, economy connected with providing of the service, infrastructure and other technical problems.

Based on the above, it is necessary to conduct (at least) the following steps::

1. Implementation of the electronics document circulation
2. Information system about Data Elements
3. Collection, summarization of the economic data
4. Simple e-Services

6.2. Poland experience

On ICT-driven local development:

1. Proper User Requirement Analysis is a must
2. Proper Project Management ensures the success
3. Information is an asset - protect it
4. Keep solutions simple
5. Maintain your documentation

1) Proper User Requirement Analysis is a must

Functional requirements analysis allows to identify and describe the desired behavior of the system. Detailed functional requirements must describe the capabilities of the system in terms of behavior and the available operations (operations performed by the system response to user actions).

Functional requirements should describe:

- how the system is achieving its objectives and business performance within a given field,
- what conditions must be met in order for the system to perform certain tasks,
- how you will be able to use the system to perform certain tasks (which application module provides specific functionality, what steps you must follow in order to achieve a given result).

In certain cases (e.g. if the requirements are few and easy to manage) it is not necessary to run the full documentation requirements - list (catalog) requirements with reference to detailed documentation is telling enough.

Proper User Requirements Analysis ensures that the system meets people needs.

2) Proper Project Management ensures the success

One of the main issues that cause projects to fail is lack of project management. The methodology of the project should use elements of recognized standards in the field of project management such as PRINCE2 and PMBOK.

PRINCE2 (Projects in a Controlled Environment) is a project management method based on a process approach. Was developed by the Office of Government Commerce, United Kingdom, was first published it in 1996. The characteristics of this method are: to examine the business case design, precise definition of the project's products and a well-defined organizational structure and the division of the project into phases and tasks. This method includes well-developed management techniques: risk, quality, changes and configurations. It is a standard in the UK and is gaining popularity in Europe.

The equivalent of the British standard in the US is the method PMBOK (A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge), developed by the Project Management Institute. It is characterized by a holistic approach to the issue of project management and also includes project management areas such as: human resources management, tendering and contracting management, communication management etc.

3) Information is an asset - protect it

Building IS one has to remember that information is a valuable asset that has to be protected.

Security is preservation of:

- confidentiality,
- integrity and
- availability of information.

Note: In addition, other properties, such as authenticity, accountability, non-repudiation and reliability can also be involved." (ISO/IEC 27000:2009)

It is very important to include security issues from the start, because implementing it later could be costly.

4) Keep solutions simple

Occam's razor, also called the principle of economy or the principle of economy of thinking – is a principle, according to which in the explanation of phenomena one should strive for simplicity, choosing such explanations, which are based on a minimum number of assumptions and concepts.

This principle can be applied to IT. The architecture of a typical system resembles a patchwork. It is a consequence of several years of practice of systems implementation. The project is characterized by a cycle: first the need, then the system analysis, architecture design, system performance, testing and finally start. Users prefer integrated solutions, i.e. one supplier provides a set of hardware, operating system, platform and sometimes even their own archiving system, authentication methods, training and system privileges. Everything remains closed within a single application, called silo.

Then the system goes into operation and improvements: new functionality to earn some extra money here, there to ensure compliance with the amended provisions elsewhere modify or print reports etc. Before the implementation there is a need for integration. The easiest way to do so is to earn some extra data exchange interfaces. Each system implemented improvement leads to an exponentially growing number of interfaces. The result is a so called „spaghetti architecture” or system, wherein the modification of one component causes a lot of hard-to-determine consequences, such as pulling out one thread of pasta with spaghetti causes movement of the whole dish.

Part of the solution would be (and often is) a change in the architecture for services-based (SOA - Service Oriented Architecture), organizing communication between systems, but this change usually encounters problems. First, the communication bus itself is a new system and requires implementation. Secondly, the need for substantial modifications of the base systems (they do not communicate directly, but through the platform and its services). Thirdly, and most importantly, in the short term, such a change does not provide direct business benefits, measured as an increase or decrease in the cost of sales, so it is difficult to obtain a sponsor within the organisation for an expensive investment.

That is why the proper design, as well as optimizations, are so important.

5) Maintain your documentation

Keeping documentation right is a very important issue. It allows new people to learn the systems details. Here are some examples of proper documentation.

Project documentation

1) The design documentation must be coherent and coordinated in all areas associated with the execution of the contract and made in such form and at such a level of detail to allow its evaluation by another independent entity, it must include:

- a) processes directing project,
- b) the structure and content of the project plans,
- c) project management techniques,
- d) a set of controls and quality management.

System Documentation

1) System documentation must include:

- a) the introduction describing the objectives and scope
- b) restrictions solutions
- c) assumptions and dependencies
- d) the general characteristics of the users
- e) a description of the functional and non-functional requirements
- f) a description of the hardware and software requirements
- g) the description and specification of interfaces
- h) the progress of the testing program and the method used to estimate the reliability of the solution, including a proposal to test reports
- i) source code (as long as they produced the project) or supplied with the software.

2) The system documentation must fully reflect the architecture of the system, its organization and all the functions provided by the system to perform, as well as administrators and users.

3) The system documentation must specify the rules and plans for installation, commissioning and implementation of the system.

4) The documentation must specify the type of system, rules and acceptance test plan reception system along with their acceptance criteria, and procedures for testing.

5) A documentation system must indicate the critical points and threats affecting the reliable operation of the system.

Operating documentation

1) Operating documentation must contain at least the following:

- a) administrative procedures,
- b) security procedures (backup)
- c) emergency procedures
- d) procedures for the user.

6.3. Slovakia experience

On ICT-driven local development:

IS users, both on government and clients sides, are an important element. As they are **end users** of the built information systems, it is necessary to think of **their needs** and involve them in the entire IS development process, including the phases of:

- analysis
- design
- testing
- pilot operation
- trainings
- awareness.

„Small” practical developments, experiences and user knowledge before setting up the robust information systems are important. Various motivation methods can be used, but less theory is preferable, with a focus on practical aspects, good examples and sharing of experiences. It can move things forward and contribute to a well developed and well used information system.

It is important to build a **good attitude** of users to **quality of data**, **systematic work**, **partner’s relationship** between users on both sides (government and citizens/entrepreneurs), **publication of information** as normal daily work, **pro-active work** and **engagement of public** in the decision making processes. Tools helping to visualize data or information can improve the work, e.g. using charts instead of big tables, using structured text instead of long articles or using Geographical information systems (GIS) which can combine information and visualize them on the map, with possibility to use also advanced functionalities of GIS for better benefit of users.

But of utmost importance is the **content** – users reading information on the web must find actual, updated information. When we stop updating information on the website when a project is finished, it is signal for the users to not visit the site anymore. This simple error leads to losing previous hours of engaging the users. Therefore the **sustainability** of systems, both from technical and content points of view is very important and needs to be taken into account when developing a project plan.

On e-services:

When developing local e-Services, it is important to start activities using a bottom-up approach and to **build a plan** on how to do it – taking into account many aspects written in this document – using the following steps:

- **organizing coalition of stakeholders** from local level with knowledge and interest, aiming to identify a single way and save resources;
- formalizing these actions by creating a **Task Force**, which will be the partner for all relevant bodies in the state and all other levels, will coordinate work on local level, communicate with central level, will lead the planning and implementation processes at the local level;
- **communicating with all stakeholders on national level** responsible for e-Transformation, targeting to keep informed about plans from central government

(including time schedules and responsibilities) and **asking for building of a common platform**, which could be used for information systems and e-Services of local government (not only HW, but also basic common applications);

- identifying the **common needs** on local level **divided in two groups**: e-Services which can be based on local data and e-Services, which require data from central/national level;
- **influencing central plans** according to the local needs;
- urgently striving to develop **electronic identification of persons**, as the basic assumption for e-Government;
- preparing concrete **Action Plan on building of IS/e-Services for local level** based on actions above;
- **allocating resources** (both human and financial);
- **organizing work to build useful IS and e-Services** for local level, while waiting for certain steps to be taken on central level – start with systematic publishing and continue building e-Service of higher level;
- **organizing events** for representatives of all local governments in the country, to be transparent, open about taking on board all the local governments not yet involved, with interest to participate and for common benefits, thus increasing the Task Force work;
- **explaining the benefits** of the Task Force work to the general public, also **motivating** them to use newly developed e-Services (e.g. via discounts of usual payments etc.)

6.4. Conclusions

The main lessons learned from the experience of Visegrad countries are:

1. Public-private partnerships are a the key to success in digitizing local services. It is for certain, that setting-up ICT departments for maintenance and especially the development of new ICT tools, in every public authority, is not feasible.
2. Interoperability remains a condition for digitization of local public services, this task being, most certainly, the responsibility of central authorities, which should develop and publish interoperability standards.
3. Digital technologies are progressing, which could repel less knowledgeable citizens. In order to ensure universal access to local digital services it is necessary to develop/purchase ICT tools, independent of certain manufacturers of digital equipment and technology, as well as to implement life-long learning programs for potential applicants of digitized local public services.
4. The digitization of local public services has a social and economic impact only when any of the services can be accessed from any public authority and are provided in a uniform manner.
5. A key role in facilitating universal access to digital services is implementing common means of identification and authentication of users, regardless of the access point and specific public authority.
6. The digitization of public services can be performed only after their successful reengineering. In many cases, preserving existing technological schemes for the

delivery of local public services remains a major obstacle to achieve efficient services and ensure universal access.

7. The change of attitude and mentality of the citizens towards the way of providing local public services based on their digitization should be a task, as important as equipping public authorities with ICT tools for electronic provision of the services.

7. Evaluation of service to be transformed in e-service

Criteria for pre-selection of ICT-based services:

- cost of implementation (within available resources)
- period of implementation (up to 12-18 months);
- e-services for citizens (G2C) and business (G2B) and less services for LPA;
- minimum back office infrastructure available;
- business processes of e-service must be defined and functional.
- urgency and relevance;
- number of beneficiaries;
- back office readiness level;
- level of complexity;
- legal and regulatory framework;
- leadership and political will;
- readiness of the beneficiary;
- sustainability;
- external factors (EU integration agenda etc.).

To evaluate the chance of selected service implementation it is useful to apply Richard Heeks ITPOSMO Model. Heeks is considered one of the founders of the ICT4D field. One of his most important contributions of the study of ICT4D is the Design-Reality Gap Model, a monitoring and evaluation tool used to measure the success of ICT4D projects, especially e-government projects.

The basis of Heeks' model is the idea that there are two points in any e-government project: the reality, that is 'where we are now,' and the goal of the project, that is 'where the e-government project wants to get us.' It's really quite simple. The larger the gap between these two points, the more difficult it is to successfully complete the project. The smaller the gap, the higher the chance of success. Heeks' claims that there are 7 dimensions, that determine this gap. These 7 dimensions are: information, technology, processes, objectives and values, staffing and skills, management systems and structures, and other resources: time and money. These 7 aspects of e-government analysis can be helpfully summed up in the acronym ITPOSMO²⁶.

Information – indicates the information used in the e-government application (comparing the information requirements contained within the design of the e-government application vs. the information currently really being used in the organisation).

Technology – indicates the technology required by the application (comparing the requirements contained within the design of the e-government application vs. the real situation now).

²⁶ Richard Heeks and the Design-Reality Gap Model <https://tulaneict4d.wordpress.com/2013/09/13/richard-heeks-and-the-design-reality-gap-model/>

Process – indicates the work processes undertaken in the agency (comparing the processes needed for successful implementation of the e-government application vs. the real situation now).

Objectives and values – indicates the objectives and values that key stakeholders need for successful implementation of the e-government application vs. their current real objectives and values.

Staffing and skills – indicates the staffing numbers and skill levels/types required in/by the agency (comparing the requirements for successful implementation of the e-government application vs. the real situation now).

Management system and structure – indicates the management systems and structures required in the agency (comparing the requirements for successful implementation of the e-government application vs. the real situation now).

Other resources – indicates such issues as the time and money required to successfully implement and operate the new application compared with the time and money really available now.²⁷

²⁷ Paper No. 22, Steering e-Government Projects from Failure to Success: Using Design-Reality Gap Analysis as a Mid-Implementation Assessment Tool. Lemma Lessa, Solomon Negash & Mesfin Belachew, 2012 http://www.seed.manchester.ac.uk/medialibrary/IDPM/working_papers/igov/igov_wp22.pdf

Figure 1. The ITPOSMO Dimensions to change in public services

For each one of the dimensions, give a numerical rating to indicate the size of the design-reality gap on that dimension. The rating for each dimension's gap can be anywhere on a scale from zero to ten. As a guide, illustrations are just given here for gaps corresponding to ratings of zero, five and ten, but all numbers in the range are possible. Illustrative ratings:

- 0 rating would indicate 'no change between the design proposal and current reality';
- 5 rating would indicate 'some degree of change between the design proposal and current reality';
- 10 rating would indicate 'complete and radical change between the design proposal and current reality'²⁸;

The simplest and crudest thing that can be done is add up the rating numbers for all seven ITPOSMO dimensions and interpret them according to the following table.

²⁸ Richard Heeks "Most e-Government-for-Development Projects Fail How Can Risks be Reduced?" IDPM 2003 <http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/cafrad/unpan011226.pdf>

Overall Rating	Likely Outcome
57 – 70	Your e-government project will almost certainly fail unless action is taken to close design-reality gaps.
43 – 56	Your e-government project may well fail unless action is taken to close design-reality gaps.
29 – 42	Your e-government might fail totally, or might well be a partial failure unless action is taken to close design-reality gaps.
15 – 28	Your e-government project might be a partial failure unless action is taken to close design-reality gaps.
0 – 14	Your e-government project may well succeed.

In addition, the scores for each individual dimension can be presented using a table or a diagram arranged to show the gaps in size order from largest to smallest.

One important issue is that e-services are parts of work processes. A process orientation should therefore be a feature of the e-service method. The e-service is also part of an IT-architecture. It is necessary to clarify issues of information exchange between the e-service and other related IT-systems. The public administration context of e-services implies different regulations and other types of norms. To know and relate to the regulations is important for achieving good processes and e-services. A normative investigation should be included in e-service development. E-service is communication (government-client communication). This e-communication is related to other kinds of communication; both human-to-human and other IT-mediated communication. Communication within a restricted domain will use linguistic elements (concepts and terminology) particularly associated with this domain (work practice).

E-services are developed to support communication between several parties and it is important that both parties understand each other. A conceptual-linguistic inquiry should also be included in e-service development. This gives five important aspects to consider during public e-service development (as illustrated in figure 2):

- Government-client communication
- Work process
- Norms (regulation & workpractice goals)
- Workpractice language
- IS-architecture & message exchange

Figure 2. Five aspects to consider

Source: Göran Goldkuhl & Annie Röstlinger, January 27-28, 2010

Future e-services should be designed contextually and integrated with the surrounding activities. **To only replace a paper form with a digital one is not often an appropriate solution for an e-service.** Appropriate measures can include both adapted e-services and other types of changes.²⁹

8. Identified Problems in ICT-based local development

The existing legal and regulatory framework provides that local authorities must offer different types of public services.

Survey data³⁰ shows that of the 22 locally supplied services, such as issuance of various documents to citizens, most in demand are: certificate about family - 20.7%; payment of taxes - 14.9%; certificate on place of residence - 13.0%; certificate about possession (loss) of share of agricultural land - 10.6%; extract from the land register - 6.1%; certificate on lack of debts to the national public budget and certificate of ownership - by 5.9%.

The other services are required in a much smaller proportion, such as certificate on lack of workbook - 0,7% or authorization of placing advertising devices - 0.8%.

The level of access of institutions and public authorities web pages for information or to obtain public services is under 25%. The most requested information concerns: medical services - 23.3%, culture - 12.3%, legislation amendments- 11.9%, governmental institutions - 11.0%.

This is explained by market underdevelopment of public services on-line (including the local absence of some of them), the perception that Internet users choose to pursue leisure and recreation interests, information functions at the expense of performance or electronics.

As the Survey found out, the lack of databases and software for electronic data processing results in increased duration of service provision. Currently, the information about the population in most municipalities is collected manually, in registers. Thus, over several

²⁹ Göran Goldkuhl & Annie Röstlinger, Linköping University, Development of public e-services - a method outline, Paper accepted to the 7th Scandinavian Workshop on E-Government (SWEG-2010), January 27-28, 2010

³⁰ Study: Servicii publice administrative prestate la nivel local: diagnostic și oportunități de e-Transformare. Elaborat cu suportul PNUD/PCDL de către: *Centrul de Investigații Sociologice și Marketing „CBS-AXA” Institutul de Dezvoltare Urbană, 2014.*

years, the mayoralties have compiled records in 9-12 registers and in order to search data about the citizen, requesting a document, time is needed to check the data from archives, books and find the necessary information. For the officials who have been working for several years in the City Hall it is much easier to find the data / information required for issuing certificates and therefore the duration is shorter.

Some municipalities have purchased cadastral programs or the "secretary plus" specialists, that facilitate the work of the LPA. Their purchases were made at the initiative of the City Hall. Municipalities that do not have such data processing programs, resort to traditional methods of work (obviously in paper records). Refusal to purchase and install electronic data processing programs is motivated by the high cost and the lack of knowledge in managing these programs.

The existing situation is also conditioned by the lack of information systems and lack of inter-networking between information systems and institutions. The lack of online and / or offline communication between the officials and institutions, to check data and information of legal or natural persons forces the beneficiary to fulfil the role of "courier" between different institutions or offices by themselves to obtain the necessary documentation. This fact justifies the urgent need to reform public services, including basic digitization and reengineering services to eliminate uncomfortable and inefficient processes.

Lack of computer software applications is one of the main difficulties related to the quick provision of local public services. Currently, in most municipalities the basic information is stored in paper records. Digitizing records and automating their management would streamline the work of public servants. However, only the digitization will not solve the problem permanently. The need for interrelated records services between institutions is also important. Interoperability of services based on PA government-to-government platform would fully optimize any flow of public services, providing opportunities for officials to extract, verify, validate, provide data registries and databases systems quickly and at minimal costs.

To implement on-line service delivery at the local level, several participants mentioned the necessity to focus on needs. As a priority, they relate to: (i) providing equipment and computers, (ii) developing procurement databases and electronic data processing programs, (iii) data processing of archive records accumulated in City Halls.

In addition to supplying equipment and technical facilities needed at the local level, there is an urgent need to reduce the number of certificates and documents required for issuing different acts.

Specialists within LPA reform implementation highlighted the need to digitize public services throughout the territory of the country, by creating *a single common system of service provision*. But first it is necessary to ensure service functionality, both technically and in terms of human resources. However, it may be emphasized and stated that local authorities are to promote and actively explore new opportunities for public services in electronic mode, including the launch of local pilot services, such as requesting and obtaining notification of payment of taxes, the certificate on place of residence, certificate about family, the extract from the Land Registry.

LPAs are also faced with a number of problems related particularly to the current organization, and especially to the insufficiency of resources for the implementation of ICT solutions, such as³¹:

- the lack of registries in hard copy of the services provided, and the lack of record keeping of services, respectively;
- insufficient resources (for e.g. cars, funds for covering the telephone costs, in some cases, the computers used are old and need to be replaced);
- the risk of discontinuing some services which are provided only by one person, whose absence makes it impossible to further provide them;
- low storage security of documents/information (for example, there is no fire alarm system for the hard copy archives in the LPA offices);
- insufficient licensed programs, lack of automated programs for documents handling;
- limited communication at the level of electronic data exchange between LPAs, DSs, and other local actors, the lack of corporative e-mail addresses.

The participants to the Discus events mainly confirmed the above-mentioned issues and underlined a range of issues in implementation of e-services on local level, such as:

- lack of political will
- lack of information campaigns for the citizen and of training for civil servants in rural areas;
- documents duplication;
- lack of pilot projects from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages which could be undertaken for multiplication in other localities;
- resistance to change;
- lack of experts group who would consult and support local authorities in e-services implementation;
- lack of a partnership network (central government, local, civil society, business etc.)
- local authorities are the main/biggest data providers, but at the same time they do not have access to these data
- necessity of a stocktaking of all public authorities possessions (in terms of ICT, information systems etc.)
- Moldova has good strategies but there is a lack of finance for a better implementation of all plans, documents.

Final Study research findings

The most requested services provided at local level, as the issuance of various documents to citizens: family composition certificates, notice of payment of taxes, the certificate on place of residence, certificate about possession (loss) of share of farmland.

ICT tools are implemented at the local level unsatisfactorily, due to lack of funds and human resources. Government support is necessary for implementation of information

³¹ Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center
<http://www.descentralizare.gov.md/lib.php?l=en&idc=446&t=/DRAFTS-IN-DISCUSSION/Concept-of-Citizen-Information-and-Service-Center>

systems at the local government level and the institutionalization of an IT advisory center for local authorities.

DISCUS platform, maintained by ISDI and supported by e-Government Center and competent central government authorities could serve as a reference platform for the exchange of information, documents, forms, etc., to support and guide the LPAs in developing ICT-based services.

Coordination and synchronization of effective and efficient assistance projects financed by donors for APL is necessary, and to exclude overlapping and duplication of efforts and activities.

Continuous support for LPAs on ICT capacity building and project management, use of tested applications, document management systems etc. is necessary

A first step towards implementing new technologies at the local level is the establishment as medium to long-term priority and allocation of resources (financial, human, etc. if possible) for the development of ICT. It is advisable that ICT-based development to be stipulated in local development strategies and other policy documents of municipalities / local councils, district councils.

Table 1. Identified issues, possible ICT based solutions for local services and recommendations on public polices for relevant public authorities

Main issues identified within workshop (March 2015)	UNDP JILDI identified issues	USAID LGSP identified issues	Briefing book from Development Partners identified issues	Main issues identified within the Seminar nr.1 (May 2015)	Main issues identified in the Public Service Reform Program	Briefing book from Development Partners recommendations	Czech relevant solution/recommendation	Polish relevant solution/recommendation	Slovak relevant solution	USAID LGSP proposed solution	Consolidated recommendations on Public polices
Certificates issuing (family composition, etc.)	Lack of digitalized registers	Services are provided in different locations (offices, floors), in the LPA premise, which fact makes it difficult for the citizens to immediately find the person(s) providing the given service(s);	Business process reengineering has lagged behind, both at the centre and in local government, and is the most important public administration challenge ahead	Lack of information campaigns for the citizen and on training for civil servants in rural area;	Incomplete information posted on the public websites	Issue a Government Decree allowing government data to be used by the private sector, academia, and local government	System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic EGON. EGON consist of: Communications infrastructure including CMS (central interconnect)	Development of e-Services needs to be done step by step. The goal of the first step should be:	Develop e-Services:	Citizen Information and Service Centre (CISC):	A. Implementation of provisions of the Public services Reform program:
Archive services / lack of record keeping of services	Lack of digitalized registers	Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant regulations, list of documents	Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.	- documents duplication;	Arbitrary inclusion of additional requirements beyond of normative acts	Approve the Law on Public Services and e-Government, in line with the EU Digital Agenda 2020, EU eGovernment Strategy and Cloud Computing Strategy;	EGON consist of: Basic registers: (People, Companies, Land and Houses, Rights and Duties)	1. Let people know that they may contact office via internet and encourage them to use.	• based on your competencies	Integrated information system of the mayor's office will be based on the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD). The ERLS and SIPD will operate on the M-Cloud platform provided by the E-	Develop and promote a draft law on public services
Cadastral Excerpts (building permits, excerpts from property register, etc.)	Lack of interoperability	Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant regulations, list of documents	Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.	- lack of pilot projects from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages which could be undertaken for multiplication in other localities;	Lack of uniform and transparent principles for establishing tariffs for paid services	Approve Policy Decisions and Regulations to enable the data exchange and interoperability through Government Platform MConnect, and to enforce the "Only	• Databoxes • Czech POINT • Governmental portal • List of OVM (Register of offices) • JIP/KAAS – unified identity space for public servants	2. Test the organisations capability in the small scale. Local authorities should consider developing the following types of Information Systems:	• make links to original sources for other relevant data		Development and promotion of the draft law on archiving electronic documents
Certificates on Tax debts	Lack of access to relevant information source	Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant regulations, list of documents	Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.	- resistance to the change;	Lack of uniform and transparent principles for establishing tariffs for paid services	Approve Policy Decisions and Regulations to enable the data exchange and interoperability through Government Platform MConnect, and to enforce the "Only	• Companies, Land and Houses, Rights and Duties)	Local authorities should consider developing the following types of Information Systems:	• without duplication of central Government work		Drafting and approving the methodolog the re-engineering of public services
Social Insurance		Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant regulations, list of documents	Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.	- lack of experts group who would consult and support local authorities in e-services implementation;	The absence of a clear definition of public services and public service diversity in legislation	Approve Policy Decisions and Regulations to enable the data exchange and interoperability through Government Platform MConnect, and to enforce the "Only	• List of OVM (Register of offices) • JIP/KAAS – unified identity space for public servants	1. Basic Internet services, 2. Document Management System, 3. GIS systems, Citizen portal.	• based on life situation of client – but complex to cover the whole process		Preparation and approval framework methodology for setting tariffs for public services rendered against payment
Services are provided in different	Lack of information systems for LPA and	Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant regulations, list of documents	Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.			Approve Policy Decisions and Regulations to enable the data exchange and interoperability through Government Platform MConnect, and to enforce the "Only	This system is intended to providing of electronics services on		• use interpretation on maps (GIS or Google		Drafting and approving public

<p>offices/no one stop-shop office</p>	<p>interoperability between decentralised services Lack of on-line/off-line communication between different public servants from different institutions</p>	<p>ments requested, terms of execution, etc.; Regardless of the fact that there are one-stop shops within LPAs, the applicants submit a set of required documents which is attached to the request by physically showing up at the mayor's office. The request for services in remote mode (via internet, telephone, fax) is not possible; □ LPAs cannot provide service in remote</p>		<p>- lack of partnership network (central government, local, civil society, business etc.)</p>	<p>The absence of unified approved guidelines on analysis and services reengineering</p>	<p>Once" Principle of Data submission by the population and businesses to government. Align Moldova Legal Framework with the EU Framework of Interoperability of Pan-European Public Service Delivery; Ensure personal data protection, as well as align relevant legislation with EU standards, and implement it effectively; and Approve and enforce cyber security policy, regulations and implementation mechanisms to ensure secure digital communication, interactions, and transactions between people, businesses and government in Moldova and in the EU Single Digital Market</p>	<p>regional and local levels. Regional services: - Regional networks interconnect - Regional shared services centres - Public services digital map - Document management. Local services: - Statutory cities shared services centres - Cities shared services centres - Czech points front offices - Public services digital map - Document management</p>	<p>The first approach to public e-services: Identify stakeholders that could be interested in going digital. Enable possibility to send applications via e-mail without the need to get to the office personally. Implement procedures that trigger right action on the side of the authority upon the receipt of the application. The resulting service might be delivered via traditional mail. Implement PKI structure so that signed applications may be treated as written ones. Identify all the procedures in the office and describe them formally – publish them on the web, along</p>	<p>maps) Make coalition of local authorities: • by developing and sharing applications • (sharing of expenditures) • Think for structure of your e-Services • the client would be not lost Take care on administrative burden !! • don't ask for data which are in Government databases • assess the real usage of all collected data in time • cancel obligations of clients when are different ways to collect data</p>	<p>Government Centre.</p>	<p>policy proposal centres on universal public services Drafting and approving the methodology for drafting administrative regulations of public services B. Implementation of The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016 C. Implementation of Government of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018 D. Implementation of Briefing book from Development Partners recommendations E. Use the relevant documents content of V4 countries provided in the Research embedded in the developed/amended documents</p>
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		mode, the physical presence of the applicant at the mayor's office is required.						with electronic version of the forms so that people could learn how to deal with their case. Transfer all the forms used in the office to active pdf (you may use tools like Scribus).			
Lack of networking (IS) between raions (LPAII) and villages (LPAI)											
Decisional transparency, lack of information										LPA Webpage	

9. Recommendations on local public e-services based on DISCUS findings & other projects activities

Given the issues identified within the Seminar discussions and taking into consideration the finding of Study³² and other above- mentioned documents, the following recommendations for promoting and implementing local public services on-line are to be taken into consideration:

- Provide public information campaigns on the benefits of on-line local public services.
- Editing and distributing tutorials on how to access and obtain e-services.
- Diversify the channels of public information on the processes taking place in local authorities, including by electronic means.
- Providing support and technical assistance, advisory to supply municipalities with equipment and modern computers.
- Promote the concept of outsourcing (outsourcing of services) and attracting investments for modernization of the LPA.
- Providing technical and specialized assistance in computer equipment maintenance for local governments.
- Provide assistance and logistical and technical support for the development of databases and electronic data processing programs.
- Provide technical and logistical assistance required to process data records from the archives accumulated in municipalities.
- Strengthen knowledge, skills of local civil servants on the use of information technology and data security and information assurance, possibly within centers of excellence in e-governance and e-public services.
- Implementation of pilot projects in local authority for testing mechanisms in providing on-line services.
- Promoting the creation of attractive conditions within municipalities for attracting and hiring young specialists.
- Operation of changes in the legal framework that would allow reduction of the number of certificates issued for local public services.
- Systemic approach, coordinated nationally, based on the principles of subsidiarity of the problems of implementation of e-services in local government.
- Conducting scientific research, studies on the premises and societal impact of electronic public services, particularly in local government, that are the main providers of services; for prioritization and objectives, identifying the best solutions and joint efforts of all social actors in the implementation of e-Government.
- Develop a suitable methodological framework to the new realities on the implementation and provision of e-services in local governments.

³² Study: Servicii publice administrative prestate la nivel local: diagnostic și oportunități de e-Transformare. Elaborat cu suportul PNUD/PCDL de către: *Centrul de Investigații Sociologice și Marketing „CBS-AXA” Institutul de Dezvoltare Urbană, 2014.*

- Encouraging the private sector and civil society to participate in developing and implementing advanced solutions for telecommunications, based on the latest achievements in information technology and communications, public management, in other relevant areas: e-commerce, e-medicine, e-education etc.
- Implementation, at LPA of pilot projects in public management solutions locally and dissemination of best practices at the national level.
- Implementation of necessary technical standards as important component for e-services
- Planning money for ICT in local budget .
- The bottom-up approach in implementation of local services - local servants should manifest initiative and wish.

Besides the listed actions, the following documents already included in action plans are to be developed, discussed, promoted and approved:

- law on public services
- law on archiving of electronic documents
- the methodology for the re-engineering of public services
- the framework methodology for setting tariffs for public services rendered against payment
- public policy proposal on centres for universal public services
- the methodology for drafting administrative regulations for public services
- the Government decision on government notification service (MNotify)
- the Government decision on government delivery service (MDelivery)
- the Government decision on the organization and functioning of the electronic document management information and records (SIGEDIA)
- the methodology for default digitization of public services
- amendments to the Regulation on single government portal content management of public services in connection with the development of the updated version (V2.0) of servicii.gov.md portal, and integration of electronic public services portal
- regulations and procedures for access and use of the interoperability platform
- Government Decision “On state Register of local authorities Regulations”

Copy this table separately for each proposed eService.

Action Plan for e-Service No.1

Model action plan for implementation.... (service name)

Problem: (problem description)				
General objective: (from Documents on strategic development of the locality, rayon, region, country)				
Goal: Implementing service (name) in LPA (locality)				
Activity/Sub-activity	Period	Responsible	Progress indicators	Monitoring Evaluation
	Start: End:		Product: Result:	
	Start: End:		Product: Result:	Intermediate: Ex-post:

Table 2: **Project Proposal Matrix**

PROJECT DESCRIPTION	INDICATORS	SOURCES OF VERIFICATION	ASSUMPTIONS
<p>Overall objective: The broad development impact to which the project contributes – at a national or sectoral level (provides the link to the policy and/or sector programme context)</p>	Measures the extent to which a contribution to the overall objective has been made. Used during evaluation. However, it is often not appropriate for the project itself to try and collect this information.	Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).	
<p>Purpose: The development outcome at the end of the project – more specifically the expected benefits to the target group(s).</p>	Helps answer the question “How will we know if the purpose has been achieved?” Should include appropriate details of quantity, quality and time.	Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).	Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage.
<p>Results: The direct/tangible results (goods and services) that the project delivers, and which are largely under project management’s control.</p>	Helps answer the question “How will we know if the results have been delivered?” Should include appropriate details of quantity, quality and time.	Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).	Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage.
<p>Activities: The tasks (work programme) that need to be carried out to deliver the planned results</p>	(sometimes a summary of resources /means is provided in this box)	(sometimes a summary of resources /means is provided in this box)	Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage.

9. Opportunities for Financial Resources for ICT-driven local development

The State Chancellery (SC) is the Central Public Administration (CPA) body that has the overall responsibility for PAR in terms of strategic planning, policy and donor coordination, monitoring and evaluation. SC is responsible over the regulatory framework related to administrative normative acts, legal status of civil servants, coordination of the decentralisation Strategy, e-Transformation agenda (through its e-Government Centre), cross border cooperation initiatives (including participation in Danube Transnational Programme) and coordination of public service modernisation National Programme.

A special platform was created to help to access the foreign financial assistance www.amp.gov.md. The Foreign Aid Management Platform (AMP) - represents an on-line data management platform of external assistance or projects, programs and other forms of assistance provided by development partners.

Through AMP platform user can follow:

- All external assistance projects have been completed, planned and ongoing having necessary information about the objectives, actions, duration and budget of the project;
- Annual reports on foreign assistance;
- Donor's profiles and normative framework;
- View the Map of Moldova areas / localities where it conducts foreign assistance

External assistance projects that are in line with national development priorities of the Government are coordinated directly with external partners (donors) and Central Public Administration (Government).

But Cross-border Cooperation Programme can be coordinated / implemented directly by local government and the European Union. To obtain the financing one has to follow strictly Donor rules, which obviously are published.

Cross-border cooperation at the external borders of the EU

The strategic objectives of the European Neighborhood Instrument (ENI) 2014-2020:

- Promoting social and economic development of regions on both sides of the border
- Troubleshooting common environmental, public health, safety and security
- Promoting better conditions for ensuring the mobility of people, goods and capital

Funding conditions:

- Projects must ensure a clear cross-border impact and added value for EU strategies and programs;
- Projects are implemented in the program area
- Not accepted duplication of financing the same actions in different EU sources
- Not accepted retroactive financing of projects.

The partnership principle

- Projects are based on cross-border partnerships between Member States and partner / candidate (Turkey);
- Each project appoint a leader to represent the partnership contract with the donor, represented by MA (is signing the financing contract);

- All partners must work actively in the development and implementation of projects and must provide personal and / or co-financing, under a partnership agreement signing it;
- Project leader receives funding from the MA and provides transfer the project to partners, according to the Partnership;
- The leader takes responsibility for the entire project implementation;
- Each partner is legally and financially responsible for the activities they implement and manage the grant it receives.

2014 – 2020 Bilateral programs successor PO ROUAMD:

1. Programme Romania-Moldova
2. Programme Romania-Ukraine
3. Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme

JOINT OPERATIONAL PROGRAMME ROMANIA-REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA 2014-2020

The program area:

The counties of Botosani, Iasi, Vaslui, Galati

The entire territory of the Republic of Moldova

Allocations: 81 million euros (ENI funds)

The minimum co-financing to ensure the two countries is 10% of the EU contribution.

Eligible projects:

Funded projects Ro-Ua-Md must fall into one of these categories:

- Integrated projects, where each partner realizes different activities on its own side of the border in order to achieve a common objective, cross-border impact;
- Symmetrical projects where similar activities are carried out in parallel Embark on border states;
- Simple projects implemented mainly or entirely in one partner country in the program but which have an impact across borders.

ELIGIBLE - potential beneficiaries can receive funding under the program, by priority and measure.

Priority 1: Towards a more competitive economy of the border area

1.1 Improving the productivity and competitiveness of urban and rural areas:

chamber of commerce, local and regional authorities, universities, other educational institutions such as business colleges, public institutions supporting the work force (job creation centers employment services employment exchanges etc.), NGOs and professional and business associations legally established public institutions responsible for promoting tourism, local associations of municipalities and municipal administrations.

1.2 Development of cooperation initiatives in transport, border infrastructure and energy networks.

Local and regional authorities, public sector entities operating in transport (railways and roads), public entities in the energy sector and public service providers, bodies responsible for border crossing management.

ELIGIBLE - potential beneficiaries can receive funding under the program, by priority and measure.

Priority 2: Environment and preparedness for emergency situations

2.1 Addressing the environmental issues, including preparing for emergencies.

Local and regional authorities, environmental agencies and agencies involved in water management and flood protection, nongovernmental organizations, administrations of national parks and protected natural areas, universities and other institutions of higher education inspectorates for emergencies, other legal bodies involved in the development of emergency plans.

2.2 Management of water resources and waste.

Local and regional organizations involved in waste management at county and regional public bodies regional and county waste water management, NGOs, non-profit organizations;

Information on ongoing projects can be found on

[//">http://amp.gov.md/viewTeamReports.do?tabs=false&language=en //](http://amp.gov.md/viewTeamReports.do?tabs=false&language=en)

<http://amp.gov.md/aim/viewNewAdvancedReport.do~view=reset&widget=false&resetSettings=true~ampReportId=1033>

Top Donors by Commitments

Donor Agency	Actual Commitments (EUR)
European Commission[65,900,421.4
International Development Agency	10,810,810.81
United States of America	7,699,178.45
Republic of Austria	6,005,100
Denmark	4,699,063.75
The Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria	2,772,080
European Union	2,750,184.56
US Department Of Defense	925,014.01
United States Department Of State	707,265.55
Food and Agriculture Organization	605,614.21

Donors' profiles and normative framework can be found at:

<http://www.amp.gov.md/portal/organizations?language=en>

Following the link further you can access the profile of any listed donor, for example Estonia <http://www.amp.gov.md/portal/node/20?language=en> and its profile will be displayed

with all available information on financing and assistance priorities and procedures. Although there are many similarities, each donor has own rules, that donor is publishing on their websites.

Accessing the link **View the profile of this donor in a dashboard** you will be guided to deeper information on assistance sectors, aid amounts of money and other information.

View the profile of this donor in a dashboard

Development partner	Estonia
Development/ Implementation agency	<p>The Ministry of Foreign Affairs is responsible for the strategic planning, implementation and coordinating the activities of different participants of Estonian development cooperation.</p> <p>Other ministries are primarily responsible for planning, implementing and evaluating development cooperation projects in their own field and for development of direct relationships with relevant institutions in developing countries, keeping in mind the goals of this Strategy.</p>
Contact details	<p>Estonia covers Moldova from the Estonian Embassy in Kiev 43B Pushkinskaya street, Kiev 01901, Ukraine Tel. +380 44 590 0780 Fax. +380 44 590 0781 Email: Embassy.Kyiv@mfa.ee Website: http://www.vm.ee/?q=en/node/74 and www.estemb.kiev.ua</p>
Legal framework for cooperation	<p>Co-operation Protocol between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Estonia and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Moldova (came into force on 03.04.1996).</p> <p>The Government of the Republic of Estonia regulation “Conditions of and Procedures for Provision of Development and Humanitarian Aid” (entered into force on 15 February 2010).</p>
Strategic documents for programming	<p>Strategy For Estonian Development Cooperation And Humanitarian Aid 2011–2015. The overall goal of Estonian development cooperation is to contribute to the eradication of world poverty and to attaining the Millennium Development Goals.</p> <p>Moldova is one of the priority partner countries for Estonia since 2006.</p>

Priority sectors/ Areas of cooperation	<p>Year EUR</p> <p>2012 – 487,000 (disbursed)</p> <p>2013 – 500,000 (planned)</p> <p>2014 – 700,000 (tentative)</p> <p>2015 – 900,000 (tentative)</p> <p>Priority sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health sector • Education/ science • Good governance/ justice • Economic development • Other
Types of funds / financial instruments and assistance modalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical assistance/Training • Grants/Scholarships
Procedures for programming, approval and implementation of projects	<p>The projects are identified by the Estonian side.</p> <p>As of 2000 Estonia’s contribution to various projects has increased tenfold. In addition to its co-operation with the Foreign Ministry, successful co-operation with Moldova has also taken place through other Estonian ministries and institutions (Ministry of Social Affairs, Ministry of the Interior, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of the Environment, Ministry of Education and Research, the National Audit Office, Academy of Security Sciences, and the Border Guard Board).</p> <p>The non-governmental sector is also showing increased interest in working in and with Moldova.</p> <p>Representatives of ministries and civil associations participate in the development cooperation project evaluation committee that approves bilateral development cooperation projects and supervises their implementation.</p>
Other information	<p>Eastern Partnership (EaP) Training Centre</p> <p>Since the beginning of 2011 the EU Eastern Partnership Training Centre started to operate in Tallinn. Based on current experiences of Estonian School of Diplomacy, training centre carries out training programmes and seminars related to various aspects of public administration reform to the EaP countries, including Moldova. The Centre is funded from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs development co-operation budget.</p>

10. Recommendations for follow-up actions

Following presentations, discussions, study researches and study visits undertaken, as well as results of questionnaires filled after each event, a list of follow-up actions should be planned:

- Maintenance of DISCUS website and platform as a reference point for keeping in touch the already created community of mayors, LPA representatives, CPA representatives, UNDP, USAID, Novateca and other representatives to discuss periodically the arisen issues on Information Society Development process.
- Institutionalising the role of the Information Society Development Institute as reference point for LPA on ICT-driven local public services, in cooperation with e-Government Center and support of the State Chancellery and Ministry of ICT.
- Generate a special project to develop and maintain methodological approach to create semantic instruments and ensure interoperability, in the Government approach in e-Governance as a whole.
- Undertake fundraising activities for creating additional capacities in ISDI for support and consultancy services for LPA.
- Create a pilot project for 2 LPAs with all necessary functionalities, as a model in ICT-based public services, to be later extended all over the country.

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Annex 1. Agendas of project events in 2015

Agenda

Workshop on ICT-driven local development

17-18.03.2015 - Chisinau, Moldova

Labour Institute, Room nr. 4, 10 Zimbrului str., Chisinau, Moldova, 2024

1st Day - March 17th			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 - 10.00	Arrival & Registration		
	1	Workshop opening	Anastasia Stefanita , Information Society Development Institute
10.00 - 10.05	1.1	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda (Ro)	Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.05 - 10.10	1.2	Welcome speech (Ro)	Acad. Gheorghe Duca , President Academy of Sciences of Moldova
10.10 - 10.15	1.3	Welcome speech (Ro)	Vitalie Tarlev , Deputy Minister of Information Technology and Communication
10.15 - 10.20	1.4	Welcome speech from the diplomatic corps of the Visegrad countries in Chisinau	(tbc)
10.20 - 10.30	1.5	DISCUS Project Presentation (Ro)	Anastasia Stefanita , ISDI Project coordinator
	2	Current situation of the ICT-driven local development in Moldova	Ion Cosuleanu , Information Society Development Institute (ISDI)
10.30 - 10.45	2.1	e-Government Transformation: Results and Priorities (Ro)	Cornelia Amihalachioae Center for Electronic Governance
10.45 - 11.00	2.2	Presentation of the Study on access and usage prospects of local public services online, Joint Integrated Local Development Programme (Ro)	Olesea Cazacu UNDP Moldova Project coordinator
11.00 - 11.15	2.3	Local Open Government based on ICT tools (Ro)	Veronica Cretu President, Open Government Institute (Moldova), member of the steering committee of the Open Government Partnership
11.15 - 11.35	2.4	Issues & Achievements at local level (Study case – Ialoveni, Moldova) (Ro)	Igor Plamadeala , Ialoveni Rayonal Council
11.35 - 12.15	2.5	Discussions on presented topics during the coffee break	All
	3	ICT-driven local development in V4 countries (good practices)	Ion Cosuleanu , Information Society Development Institute
12.15- 12.50	3.1	Local e-services - good practices in Poland (Eng)	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert Poland
		Q&A session	
12.50 - 13.25	3.2	Important system points by building local e-services based on Slovakia practices (Eng)	Vladimir Benko Expert Slovakia
		Q&A session	

13.25 - 14.00	3.3	Methodological approaches on ICT-driven local development (including e-services) (Eng) Q&A session	Vratislav Datel Expert Czech Republic
14.00 - 14.50	Lunch		
14.50 - 15.20	3.4	Discussions on V4 best practices. Recommendations for Moldova	Facilitators: Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy (IPP) Ion Cosuleanu , ISDI
	4	Focus groups work	
15.20 - 16.30	4.1	Focus groups work (3 groups*approx. 10 persons) Topics to be identified based on presentations and Q&A sessions	Facilitator : Veronica Cretu President, Open Government Institute (Moldova), member of the steering committee of the Open Government Partnership
16.30 - 17.30	4.2	Presentations of 3 focus groups work results & coffee break	
17.30 - 18.10	4.3	Final discussions & conclusions	Facilitators: Anatol Gremalschi IPP, Ion Cosuleanu , ISDI
18.10 - 19.30	Networking event		
2nd day – March 18th			
	5	Action plan for local e-services implementation	
		Mihai Grecu , Information Society Development Institute	
09.00 - 09.30	5.1	Proposals for development of the Action Plan Draft for local e-services implementation	Vratislav Datel Expert Czech Republic
09.30 - 09.40		Q&A	
09.40 - 10.10	5.2	Recommendations/Useful advices on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert Poland
10.10 - 10.20		Q&A	
10.20 - 10.35	5.3	Recommendations/Useful advices on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities	Vladimir Benko Expert Slovakia
10.35 - 10.45		Q&A session	
10.45 - 11.45	Coffee Break & Discussions		
	6	IT Performance Centers - concept	
		Anatol Gremalschi , Program director, Institute for Public Policy	
11.45 - 12.05	6.1	General presentation of IT Performance Centers idea (Look@IT study results)	Ion Cosuleanu , ISDI
12.05 - 12.20	6.2	IT Performance Centers Concept. Issues & possible solutions	Ion Cosuleanu , ISDI
12.35 - 12.50	6.3	Digital content and motivation of youths	Vladimir Benko Expert Slovakia
12.50 - 13.50	6.4	Discussions on IT Performance Centers Concept	Facilitators: Anatol Gremalschi , IPP, Ion Cosuleanu , ISDI
13.50 - 14.50	Lunch		
14.50 - 15.30	Final discussions & conclusions of the event		
15.30 - 16.00	Feedback questionnaire		
16.00 - 17.00	Coffee Break & final organisational issues		
17.00 - 17.30	Wrap-up & Departure		

DISCUS is a project coordinated by the [Information Society Development Institute](#), with the support of partners from Visegrad countries and funded under the [International Visegrad Fund](#)

Agenda

Scientific Seminar: ICT solutions for Local Services (legal regulations)

26 - 27.05.2015 - Chişinău, Moldova

Labour Institute, Room no. 6, Zimbrului 10 str. , Chişinău - 2024, Moldova

1 st Day – May 26 th			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.00 - 09.30	Arrival & Registration		
	1	Seminar opening	Igor Cojocaru, IDSI (M)
09.30 - 09.40	1.1	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
09.45- 09.55	1.2	Welcome speech	Acad. Gheorghe Duca , president of the Academy of Science of Moldova
10.00 - 10.10	1.3	Welcome speech	Andrei Cuşcă , Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
10.15 - 10.25	1.4	Welcome speech from the diplomatic corps of the Visegrad countries in Chisinau	
10.25 - 10.30	1.5	Welcome speech	Ceauş Sergiu , Deputy General Secretary of the Government
10.30 - 10.45	1.6	Presentation of the I st project study research	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy (IPP)
	2	National Legal Regulations on ICT in Local Public Administration	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
10.55 - 11.20	2.1	National strategy "Digital Moldova 2020" - a basic policy document on development of the information society in Moldova	Andrei Cuşcă , Deputy Head, Department of Information Technology policies, the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
11.25 - 11.55		Discussions & Coffee Break	
12.00 - 12.30	2.2	The legal framework for the e-Transformation Agenda of the Governance	Eduard Fricatel , Legal Consultant, Center for Electronic Governance
12.35 - 13.05	2.3	Center for Information and Services of Orhei City Hall and the Geographic Information System Orhei	Igor Cernei , Specialist City Hall Orhei
13.10 - 13.55		Lunch	
14.00 - 14.25	2.4	Development and institutionalization of effective communication with citizens instruments (1.0 WebAPL platform)	Petru Culeac , Community Mobilization Consultant, USAID Local Government Support Project in Moldova
	3	Good V4 countries practices	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy

14.30 - 15.00	3.1	Information Technology Strategic Planning by local authorities (Part I)	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
15.05 - 15.35	3.2	Open self-government: City Presov - systematic and effective building of info services	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
15.40 - 16.10	3.3	Legislation and technical standards in Public Administration (part I)	Vratislav Datel Expert from Czech Republic
16.15 - 16.50		Coffee Break	
	4	e-Government platforms in Moldova	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
16.55 - 18.20	4.1	e-Government platforms, implemented for central public authorities and available for reuse by local authorities	Iurie Țurcanu, Chief Technological Coordinator, Deputy Director Center for Electronic Governance
18.20 - 18.30	4.2	Final discussions & conclusions	Anatol Gremalschi - IPP Ion Coşuleanu - ISDI
18.30 - 19.30	Networking event		
2nd Day – 27 May			
	5	Good V4 countries practices	Mihai Grecu, IDSI (M)
09.00 - 09.30	5.1	Legislation and technical standards in Public Administration (part II)	Vratislav Datel Expert from Czech Republic
09.35 - 10.05	5.2	Information Technology Strategic Planning by local authorities (Part II)	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
10.10 - 10.40	5.3	ICT tools for environment management for local authorities - recommendations for Moldova	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
10.40 - 11.00		Q&A session	
11.00 - 11.45		Coffee Break	
11.50 - 12.20	6.1	Interoperability - an opportunity to modernize local public services	Mihai Grecu, IDSI
12.20 - 12.45		Final discussions & conclusions of the event	
12.50 - 13.20		Handing participation certificates	
13.20 - 13.30		Feedback questionnaire & final organisational issues	
13.30 - 14.10		Lunch	
14.10 - 14.30		Wrap-up & Departure	

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Agenda

Workshop: Local Public e-Services

22 - 23.09.2015 - Chisinau, Moldova

Labour Institute, Room no. 6, 10 Zimbrului str., Chisinau, Moldova, 2024

1st Day – September 22			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 - 10.00	Arrival & Registration		
	1	Workshop opening	Igor Cojocar, IDSI (M)
10.00 - 10.10	1.1	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	Igor Cojocar Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.15- 10.25	1.2	Welcome speech	Acad. Ion Tighineanu , Vice-president Academy of Sciences of Moldova
10.25 - 10.35	1.3	Welcome speech	Andrei Cușcă , Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
10.40 - 10.50	1.4	Welcome speech	Ceaș Sergiu , Deputy General Secretary of the Government
10.50 - 11.25	1.5	Presentation of the II nd project study research based on the seminar (from may) findings	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy (IPP)
		Q&A session	
11.30 - 12.00		Pauză de cafea	
	2	Study visit to Poland - lessons learnt	
12.00 - 12.35	2.1	Study visit to Poland - July 5 - 10, 2015	Anastasia Stefanita , ISDI Project coordinator *** participants
	2.2	Discussions with participants at the study visit	
	3	Action Plan: Local Public e-Services	
12.40 - 13.00	3.1	Recommendations for writing an action plan (template, suggestions)	Ion Coșuleanu , ISDI V4 experts
13.00 - 13.40	3.2	Explaining the exercise/task. Formation of the working teams. Formation the Evaluation Commission.	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy (IPP) Ion Coșuleanu , ISDI
13.40 - 14.30		Lunch	
	4	Working in groups	
14.40 - 16.40	4.1	Working in groups (coordinated by DISCUS experts)	
16.20 - 16.50		Coffee break & Discussions	
16.50 - 18.00	4.2	Working groups presentations	Ion Coșuleanu , ISDI
18.00 - 19.00	Networking event		

2nd Day - September 23			
	5	Final action plans	
09.00 - 09.20	5.1	Analyse of the working groups presentations. Discussions.	DISCUS experts
09.25 - 09.45	5.2	Evaluation Commission opinion. Selection of the best two action plans.	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
09.50 - 10.40	5.3	Work in 2 groups on finishing the 2 selected action plans	DISCUS experts
10.45 - 11.00	5.4	Recommendations on finalizing plans	Anatol Gremalschi, IPP
11.00 - 11.30		Coffee break	
	6	Project: eServices & document circulation	
11.30 - 11.45	6.1	Presentation of the project: eServices of Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of Slovakia	Vlado Benko , expert from Slovakia
11.45 - 12.15	6.2	System of electronic document circulation in public management ANOFM & Czech partners	Stanislav Horák , expert in document circulation, DATAB consult, s.r.o., Czech Republic
12.15 - 12.30		Experts answers to participants' questions	DISCUS experts
12.30 - 12.45		Final discussions & conclusions of the event	
12.50 - 13.15		Handing participation certificates	
13.15 - 13.30		Feedback questionnaire	
		Final organisational issues	
13.30 - 14.30		Lunch	
14.30 - 15.00		Wrap-up & Departure	

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Agenda

Seminar: ICT-based Solutions for Local Services (Practical Aspects)

November 24 – 25, 2015 - Chisinau, Moldova

Labour Institute, Conference Hall – 1st level, 10 Zimbrului str., Chisinau, Moldova, 2024

Day 1 – November 24		
Time	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 - 10.00	Arrival & registration	
	Welcome coffee	
10.00 - 10.10	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	dr. Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.15- 10.25	Welcome speech	Acad. Ion Toghineanu , prime-vicepresident of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova
10.30 - 10.40	Welcome speech	Ceaus Sergiu , Deputy General Secretary of the Government
10.40 - 10.50	Welcome speech	Andrei Cusca , Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications
10.50-11.15	General and practical aspects regarding personal data protection	Sergiu Arsene, Sergiu Bozianu National Center for Personal Data Protection
11.15-11.40	Funding instruments for LPAs project from external sources	Victor Nicolaescu, Alexandru Rusu State Chancellery
11.40-12.15	Discussions & Coffee break * Common photo	
12.15- 13.05	Reusable government electronic services	Dumitru Postu, Sergiu Bedros E-Government Center
13.10-13.25	Participants introductions (First name/Last name, Locality, Position)	All participants
13.30-14.20	Lunch	
14.30-14.55	“.MD” domain for LPAs: penetrability, goals and reality	Dorian Bodi , MoldData
15.00 - 15.25	IT instruments for LPAs	Olesea Cazacu , Project manager, Local Development and Migration Eugent Platita , IT consultant, Joint Integrated Program for Local Development
15.30-15.50	ICT solutions for LPAs (practical recommendations)	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
16.00 - 16.30	Discussions & Coffee break	
16.30-16.55	Some suggestions concerning local e-services to be developed	Vratislav Datel Expert from the Czech Republic

17.00-17.30	Novateca program	Maria Gonta , Novateca
17.30-17.50	TAP SYSTEM (example of outputs based on feedback questionnaires of Study Visit participants in Slovakia)	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
17.50 - 18.10	Final discussions & conclusions of the event	Anatol Gremalschi - IPP Ion Cosuleanu - IDSI
18.15 - 19.30	Dinner & Networking event	
Day 2 – November 25		
09.00 - 09.30	Study visit in Slovakia: good practices	Anastasia Stefanita , IDSI study visit participants
09.30-10.00	ISDI services – opportunities for LPAs	Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.00 – 10.20	Exemple of IT implementation program in LPA – I part	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
10.20 – 10.45	Coffee break	
10.50-11.15	Exemple of IT implementation program in LPA – I part	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
11.20- 11.50	Households Register. Conceptual approach	Mihai Grecu , Information Society Development Institute
11.50 – 12.30	Discussions: Electronic Households Register – necessary steps	Anatol Gremalschi , IPP Ion Cosuleanu , IDSI Mihai Grecu , IDSI
12.30 - 12.50	Seminar conclusions	
12.50 - 13.15	Handing participation certificates	
13.15 - 13.30	Feedback questionnaire	
	Final organisational issues	
13.30 - 15.00	Lunch	
15.00	Participants departure	

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USM
www.usm.md

Agenda

Masă rotundă „*Valorificarea patrimoniului științific național prin conținut digital*”

5 iunie 2015, începând cu ora 10:00, în cadrul Universității de Stat din Moldova
(or. Chișinău, str. A.Mateevici, 60, Blocul Central, et. 2, Sala Senatului).

Moderator - Nelly Țurcan, dr.hab., USM

5 iunie 2015			
Ora	Nr.	Subiect/prezentare	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 – 10.00		Înregistrarea	
	1	Sesiune de discuții „Politici și strategii privind conținutul digital din Republica Moldova”	
10.00 - 10.30	1.1	Cuvânt de salut	Dr., conf. univ. Angela Niculiță , Prorector pentru relații internaționale a USM Vitalie Tarlev , Viceministru al Tehnologiei Informației și Comunicațiilor Dr. Igor Șarov , Viceministru al Culturii Dr. hab. A.Hanganu , Secretar științific general al AȘM Dr. Lidia Kulikovski , Programul Novateca
10.30 - 10.45	1.2	Analiza politicilor naționale privind crearea de conținut digital până în 2020	Dr. Igor Cojocar Director, Institutul de Dezvoltare a Societății Informaționale (15 min)
10.50 - 11.05	1.3	Abordări privind realizarea pilonului Conținut digital și servicii electronice din Strategia Națională „Moldova Digitală 2020”	MTIC , (15 min)
11.10 - 11.25	1.4	Dreptul de autor și contribuția AGEPI la valorificarea patrimoniului științific prin conținut digital	Dr. Lilia Bolocan , Director general, AGEPI (15 min)
11.30 - 12.15	1.5	Discuții. Intervenții	45 min.
12.15 - 12.45		Pauză. Coffee break	30 min.
	2	Sesiune de prezentare a bunelor practici privind digitizarea, crearea și utilizarea conținutului digital	
12.45 - 12.55	2.1	Orientări și tendințe în digitalizarea patrimoniului cultural. Practica Bibliotecii Naționale Digitale Moldavica	Diana Lupușor , Șef Serviciu Numerizare, Biblioteca Națională a Republicii Moldova (10 min)
13.00 - 13.10	2.2	Eldorado – acces online la documente digitizate din colecțiile bibliotecilor	Diana Ghiorgheș , Country manager, Qulto România (10 min)
13.15 - 13.25	2.3	Revista SUM – platformă de promovare a rezultatelor științifice	Ceban Lilia , Coordonator Revista SUM, USM (10 min)
13.30 - 13.40	2.4	Metode, instrumente și tehnici de digitizare a materialelor fonogramice de teren și a datelor și informațiilor scrise cu caracter etnografic	Dr. Ion Duminică , Seful Secției „Minorități etnice”, Institutul Patrimoniului Cultural al AȘM (10 min)
13.45 - 13.55	2.5	Programele analitice ale disciplinelor – prezențe în bazele de date instituționale	Ludmila Corghenci , Director, Biblioteca ULIM (10 min)
14.00 - 14.30	3	Concluzii. Recomandări	

Agenda

Round Table

Digital National Content for Public Access

December 9, 2015 - Chişinău, Moldova

Conference Room – I floor, Academiei 5A str.

Time	Topic/Presentation	Speaker/Expert
9.30 - 10.00	Arrival & registration Welcome coffee	
10.00 - 10.10	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	dr. Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.10 – 10.30	Peculiarities of scientific journals in Moldova	acad. Leonid CULIUC , Chairman of the The evaluation committee of scientific journals
10.30 – 10.50	Discussions Q&A	acad. Leonid CULIUC
10.50 – 11.20	National and international objectives on improving scientific content in digital format	dr. Igor COJOCARU Director, IDSI
11.20 – 11.40	Open Access Policy	dr. hab. Nelly Țurcan , State University of Moldova
11.40 – 12.10	National Bibliometric Instrument – a tool to assist the editorial board and researchers	dr. Igor COJOCARU Director, IDSI
12.10 – 13.00	Discussions: IT tools for national scientific content	dr. hab. Nelly Țurcan , State University of Moldova
13.00 – 13.30	Conclusions Final Remarks	dr. Igor Cojocaru, IDSI
13.30 – 15.00	Lunch break & discussions	
15.00	Wrap-up & Departure	

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Agenda

Study tour in Poland

July 6-10, 2015

Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform

Day 1. – July 6 (Monday) - Welcome!	
- FRSI – Information Society Development Foundation: key activities and achievements	
10:00	Arrival participants from Chisinau at the Chopin Airport, Warsaw, Poland Meeting at the airport by FRSI representative and check in at B & B Boutique Hotel, (www.bedandbreakfast.pl), Smolna 14 str.
13:00-14:00	Lunch, restaurant „Kamanda Lwowska”, Foksal 10 str.
14:30-17:00	Office FRSI, Puławska 14 str. Meeting with FRSI representative and GEOPOLIS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the study tour agenda ▪ Managementul municipal - soluție de tip "smart city», Sistemul de Informații Geografice (GIS - Geographic Information System) - Paul Shmayda, GEOPOLIS. ▪ Presentation of Library Development Program (2009-2015) and international activity of FRSI
18:00	Dinner
Day 2. – July 7 (Tuesday) – Piotrków Trybunalski:	
Experience exchange – e-services and new technologies for citizens at the local level	
7:15	Meeting in front of hotel
8:00-10:12	Departure by train to Piotrkow Trybunalski (central railwaystation Warsaw)
11:00-13:30	Visit to the City Hall of Piotrkow Trybunalski Online services: document management system, e-learning platform Piotrkowska, Solutions GIS (Geographic Information System), credible profile concept, confirmation of profiles, Citizen Service Bureau
14:00-15:00	Lunch – old city center Piotrkow Trybunalski
15:30-17:30	Visit to Public Library “Adam Puhnik” of Piotrkow Trybunalski city and Filial nr.1 of the Library Project: Innovative area - held in colaboration with the FRSI, functioning of the modern public library
18:28-20.30	Return to Warsaw. Dinner in the hotel.
Day 3. – July 8 (Wednesday) – Warszawa, Zielonka	
– implementation of e-services at the national and local level	
8:30	Breakfast. Meeting in front of the hotel.
9:30–11:00	Meeting at the Ministry of Justice, IT and court registers Department, Czerniakowska 100 str., III p., of.338) Electronic Cadastral books
12:30–14.30	Visit to City Hall of Zielonka city, Lipowa 5 str. Online services: recruitment of children in the kindergarten, text messages, e-mail inbox, on-line transmission of the City Council meetings
15:00–16.00	Lunch, departure to Warsaw

19:00	Dinner at the restaurant „Opasły tom”, Foksal 17 str.
Day 4. – July 9 (Thursday) Kraków - The formation of the information society and online services at the regional level	
5:45	Check-out
6:33-8:57	Departure by train to Piotrkow Trybunalski (central railway station Warsaw) Check in at “Monika” hotel, Mariana Langiewiczza 6 str., www.hotelmonika.pl
11:00 – 16.00	Visit to Central Office of Malopolska Voivodship , Raclawicka 56 str. Online services: document management system; video communication system of the institution with citizens; e-learning system; Virtual museums in the region.
16.30 – 18.00	Lunch Meeting with polish DISCUS expert – Mr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz
Day 5. – July 10 (Friday) – evaluation of the study visit	
6:15	Departure from Krakow by train to Warsaw
10:15-12:15	Meeting at FRISI office , Puławska 14 str. Evaluation session – Anastasia Stefanita, IDSI Evaluation questionnaires & discussions
12:30-13:30	Lunch – Restaurant Wiking, Puławska 2 str. (Plac Unii)
13:45	Departure to Airport Flight time –16:05

Agenda

Study Visit in Slovakia

04 – 09 October 2015

1st Day – October 04, Sunday			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
16.40	Arrival to Vienna airport		
	Transport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to Bratislava by BUS on road Vienna airport – Bratislava Bus station • to the hotel Safron in Bratislava by car Accommodation – Hotel Saffron Bratislava		
	Dinner		
2nd Day – October 05, Monday			
	Breakfast in hotel		
08.30	Departure from hotel by car		
	1	Opening and the 1st block	<i>VIK, Zahradnicka 51, Bratislava</i>
09.00 -	1.1	Study Visit Information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • overview of the Agenda and the Goals • presentations of participants • aspects of building Information Society 	Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková Alexander Jančárik StudyVisit participants
	1.2	Discussion with Visegrad Fund Program Manager	Lenka Bučková, Visegrad Fund
	1.3	PPP - How Civil Association is dealing with Information Society	Milan Ištván, PPP
- 12.30	1.4	Q&A session	
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch		
13.30 - 15.00	1.5	Study Visit Information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • important aspects of building eServices / SMART cities approach • example of small village Horna Ves 	
	2	The 2nd block	<i>CVTI SR, Lamačská cesta 8, Bratislava</i>
15.30 -	2.1	Scientific information sources of Center of Scientific-Technical Information of SR (CVTI SR)	Ľubomír Bilský, Center of Scientific Technical Information (CVTI) Vladimír Benko, proIS, Alexander Jančárik
- 17.30	2.2	Discussion	
	Dinner		

3rd Day – October 06, Tuesday			
	Breakfast in hotel		
08.30	Departure from hotel by car		
	3	The 3rd block	<i>MPSVaR SR, Špitálska 4, Bratislava</i>
09:30 -	3.1	eServices of Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of SR	Jozef Snopko, Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of SR Vladimír Benko, proIS
- 12.00	3.2	Discussion	
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch		
	4	The 4th block	<i>DEUS, Kýčerského 5, Bratislava</i>
14:00 -	4.1	DCOM – Datacenter of Vilages and Cities	Rudolf Horváth, DEUS Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková, Alexander Jančárik
- 16:30	4.2	Discussion	
	Dinner		
4th Day – October 07, Wednesday			
	Breakfast in hotel		
08.30	Departure from hotel		
			on foot
	5	The 5th block	<i>Slovenská pošta, Nám.SNP 35, Bratislava Magistrát hl.mesta SR, Primaciálne nám.1, Bratislava</i>
09:00 -	5.1	IOM – Integrated Service Points	Slovak Post Vladimír Benko, proIS
	5.2	Clients' center in City Office Bratislava	Marek Papajčík, City office Bratislava Jiří Bukvic, Vratislav Datel, DATAB Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková, Alexander Jančárik
- 11:00	5.3	Discussion	
11:30 -	Departure to Nitra		by car from Hotel Saffron
12:30-13:30	Lunch		
	6	The 6th block	<i>Mestský úrad Nitra, Štefánikova 60 Hotel The Grand Víglaš</i>
14:00 – 16:30	6.1	eServices for citizens of city Nitra	Richard Cíváň, City office Nitra Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková, Alexander Jančárik Jiří Bukvic, Vratislav Datel, DATAB
17:30 -	6.2	Tourist and Congress destination The Grand Viglas	Daniela Baleková, The Grand Víglaš
19:00 -	Dinner		Dragon cellar
5th Day - October 08, Thursday			
7:30 – 8:15	Breakfest in hotel		
8:15 – 9:00	Guided castle tour, explanation of operation		Daniela Baleková, The Grand Víglaš
09.00	Departure from hotel by car		
	7	The 7th block	<i>Radnica mesta Banská Bystrica, Nám.SNP 1 Múzeum SNP, Kapituslká 23,Banská Bystrica GAMO, Kyjevské nám 6, Banská Bystrica</i>

10:00 -	7.1	Information Point Banska Bystrica	Zuzana Kučerová, Town Hall Banska Bystrica Vladimír Benko, proIS
	7.2	Smart City Zone by Monument of Slovak National Uprising (SNP)	Museum of SNP Roland Schwarz, GAMO, a.s. Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková
11:30 -	7.3	Principles of Smart zones, data usage, ... TAP – questionnaires, assessments, surveys	Ján Lichvár, Karin Vlčeková, Roland Schwarz, Marcela Gottwaldová, GAMO, a.s. Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková
- 12:30	7.4	Discussion	
12:30 – 13:30		Lunch	
	8	The 8th block	<i>ŠVK Banská Bystrica, Lazovná 9</i>
14:00 – 17:00	8.1	eServices of State Scientific Bibliothek	Olga Lauková, Olga Doktorová, State Scientific Bibliothek Banska Bystrica Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková, Alexander Jančárik
17:30 -	8.2	Accommodation	Hotel Dixon Banská Bystrica
18:30 -		Dinner	
6th Day - October 09, Friday			
		Breakfast in hotel	
08.30		Departure from hotel by car	
	9	The 9th block	<i>SAŽP, Tajovského 28, Banská Bystrica proIS, Na Troskách 12, Banská Bystrica</i>
09:00 -	9.1	IS EIA/SEA – information support and public participation on decision making processes	Katarína Palúchová, Mária Hrnčárová, Katarína Kováčová, Martin Koška, Slovak Environmental Agency Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková, Alexander Jančárik
- 11:30	9.2	Discussion	
11:45 -	9.3	Project DISCUS administration	Vladimír Benko, proIS Anastasia Stefanita, IDSI
12:15 – 13:15		Lunch	
	10	The 10th block	<i>proIS, Na Troskách 12, Banská Bystrica</i>
13:30 -	10.1	Services of coworkingBB	Vladimír Benko, proIS, coworkingBB Elena Bodíková, Alexander Jančárik
14:00 -	10.2	Reporting and final discussion	Vladimír Benko, proIS Elena Bodíková
-15:30		Wrap-up & Departure to Bratislava	
18:00 -		Snack	<i>Bratislava</i>
19:00 -		Departure to Vienna airport by bus	<i>Bus station Bratislava Nivy</i>

Working program will be in English and Slovak, Translation sk/en

DISCUS is a project coordinated by the [Information Society Development Institute](#), supported by partners from V4 countries and funded under the [International Visegrad Fund](#)

Annex 2: Project Factsheets on DISCUS activities 2015

January-December 2015
<http://www.discus.idsi.md/>
<https://www.facebook.com/DISCUS.IDSI>

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Visegrad Fund

AIM
Promotion of the European model of effective application of information society policies/ e-Governance tools in Moldova to strengthen participation of academic sector, local government, business, civil society, mass-media in decision making process, using the experience of V4 countries.
 A special **communication platform** (periodic seminar on Information Society development issues) will be established to achieve the project goal and further facilitate political association with EU.

a project coordinated by the
Information Society Development Institute

ACTIVITIES

- **2 Workshops** for local public representatives, civil society organisations and SMEs (involving study cases) **on ICT-driven local development.**
- **2 Study visits** in Visegrad countries of several visionaries selected from local public representatives, to support **knowledge transfer and collaboration.**
- **Draft action plan** for implementation of **local e-services in 2 selected rural localities**, taking into account the opportunities for PPPs at the local level.
- **2 Seminars** with representatives of academic sector, government, business, civil society, mass-media and V4 experts **on Information Society development issues.**
- **Recommendations on public policies, regulations etc. amendments** for the relevant public authorities **based on V4 best practices and findings of seminars.**

Information Society Development Institute
 Republic of Moldova
www.idsi.md

Information Society Development Foundation
 Poland
www.frsi.org.pl

1 EaP partner
3 V4 partners

proIS, s.r.o.
 Slovakia
www.prois.sk

DATAB consult s.r.o.
 Czech Republic
www.datalab.cz

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DISCUS is a project funded under the International Visegrad Fund
<http://visegradfund.org/>

EXPECTED IMPACTS

- **Local Public Authorities** representatives will benefit through enhancing their **institutional capacity for participation in the decision-making process on central level.**
- **Study visits** will contribute to **exchange of best-practices**, as well as strengthening **collaboration with V4 countries.**
- The **draft action plan** for implementation of local e-services will boost the **ICT-driven local development** and will lead to **improved citizen services.**
- **Policy making authorities** will benefit from **extended networking** with representatives of academic sector, business, civil society, mass-media and V4 experts on Information Society development issues.
- **Recommendations on public policies' amendments based on V4 best practices** and the input of seminars' participants will contribute towards **enhanced policy/legal/regulatory documents.**

<h1 style="margin: 0;">DISCUS</h1> <p style="margin: 0;">Workshop on ICT-driven local development</p>	<p style="margin: 0;">17-18 march 2015 Chişinău</p>
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35
application forms

over **55**
participants

26 local public representatives

Representatives of:

- academic sector

- governmental sector

- civil society

- mass-media

Ideas of e-services &
actions of their
implementation at the
local level in Moldova

3 Visegrad Experts

10 Local Experts

Discussions and
Teamwork

15
presentations

DISCUS
 Scientific seminar: ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations)

**26-27 may
 2015
 Chişinău**

over **50**
 participants

35
 application forms

25 local public representatives

Representatives of:

- civil society

- academic sector

- governmental sector

**Research study
 Ro & Eng**

3 Visegrad Experts

6 Local Experts

13
 presentations

DISCUS

Study visit to Poland

6 - 10 July
2015
Chişinău

4 local representatives from Moldova

1 responsible for international relations in IDSI

10 application forms

20 presentations:

- electronic systems
- electronic services
- equipments and IT solutions in the public sector

10 visited institutions:

- Ministries/Departments
- City Halls
- Libraries
- NGOs
- Central Office of Malopolska Voivodship
- Offices that provide public services

4 visited cities:

- Warsaw
- Piotrkow Trybunalski
- Zielonka
- Kraków

Poland

DISCUS

Study visit in Slovakia

october 5 - 9
2015

3

public local servants from
Moldova (Hincesti, Orhei,
Singerei)

2

researchers
Information Society
Development Institute

20 presentations:

- e-services
- IT systems
- educational software

15 visited institutions:

- ministries
- state agencies
- town halls
- IT companies
- S&T centres
- museums
- libraries
- NGOs

4 visited localities:

- Bratislava
- Nitra
- Viglas
- Banska Bystrica

Slovakia

<h1 style="margin: 0;">DISCUS</h1> <p style="margin: 0;">Seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (practical aspects)</p>	<p style="margin: 0;">24-25 november 2015 Chisinau</p>
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over **120**
participants

12
presentations

The seminar was attended by:

15 mayors

**20 deputy mayors,
secretaries of
local/district councils**

**20 representatives
of libraries,
schools/colleges/
universities**

The event was attended by:

- ✓ **Acad. Ion Tighineanu, senior vice president of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova**
- ✓ **Sergiu Ceaus, Deputy Secretary General of the Government**
- ✓ **Andrei Cusca, Ministry of Information Technology and Communications**
- ✓ **Dr. Veaceslav Ursachi, head of the Engineering and Technology Sciences Department of ASM**

3 Visegrad Experts

14 Local Experts

